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D4.5 Living Lab Guidelines (first version).

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Abbreviations

AAFC	Agriculture and agri-food Canada
ALLIN	Australian Living Lab Innovation Network
APRILab	Action oriented research on Planning, Regulation, and Investment dilemmas in a Living lab experience
DESIRA	Digitisation: Economic and Social Impacts in Rural Areas
E&I	Equipment & infrastructure
EC	European Commission
ENoLL	European Network of Living Labs
EU	European Union
FMS-Lab	Future Mobility Solutions-lab
Forum LLSA	Le Forum des Living Labs en Santé et en Autonomie
FTE	Full Time Equivalent
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
HR	Human Resources
IAP2	International Association for Public Participation
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IP	Intellectual property
IPR	Intellectual property rights
JRC	Joint Research Centre
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LIAISON	Living Lab business model canvas
LL	Living Lab
LSSLN	Lake Superior Living Lab Network
PhD	Doctorate of Philosophy
RI	Research Infrastructure
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal

SMART	Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant & Time-bound
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities & Threats
TLLCMM	Transnational Living Lab Collaboration Maturity Model
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UFE	Utilization Focused Evaluation
WeLL	Wallonia eHealth Living Lab
WP	Work Package
WG	Working group

Executive summary

A harmonization of the living lab concepts and the necessary steps for setting up and running living labs via a validated framework as mentioned by Kalinauskaitė & all (2021)¹ is an evident need to providing organizations with clear guidelines to become a (harmonized) living lab. Doing so, increases the sustainability of these organizations.

Often organizations are so-called living labs, while they are not. And the other way around, sometimes they are living labs while they don't call themselves that way. Towards this end, VITALISE aims to create a guideline framework, supporting living labs in harmonizing the living lab concepts and help living labs in their growing pathways towards sustainability and harmonization. This document presents the work performed in the creation of a guideline framework for living labs.

First it reports on the scoping of the guideline framework (2.1) and provides information about the executed desktop research around living lab guidelines and harmonization (2.2). After presenting the applied methodology of the desktop research (2.2.1) it describes the main outcomes of this desktop research (2.2.2), focusing on the crucial elements and definitions to be included into the guideline framework.

Next to this, the document sheds light on the work done around the establishment of an evaluation framework (2.3) to support this guideline framework by clarifying the purpose of the evaluation framework (2.3.2), the methodology applied (2.3.3) and the outcomes up to this moment (2.3.4).

This last section provides insights into the performed literature review on the evaluation of living labs (2.3.4.1), together with the applied desktop research on evaluation frameworks within ENoLL projects (2.3.4.2) and external assessment frameworks (2.3.4.3). Furthermore, it describes the results of this literature review and desktop research, including an overview of the updated evaluation framework and its criteria descriptions (2.3.4.5), together with a defined KPI table for evaluating living labs in general (2.3.4.6)

Based on these inputs the overall guideline framework existing out of three chronological phases: onboarding, running and harmonization, is presented within section 2.4. Following this, the document provides more elaborative insights in each of the ten steps of the first version of the guideline framework within section 3 (Step by step).

This first version of the guideline framework is offering the structure for the further development of it in the upcoming 12 months. The next steps which are planned for are sketched in section 4 of this document. Finally, the authors present their conclusions in section 5.

The design of this guideline framework is done in a utilization focused approach, involving key internal (Vitalise pilot group and harmonization board) and external (ENoLL labelling task force and group of academic living lab experts) stakeholders in the whole process. Following this approach is safeguarding that the outcomes of this first version and the final version of the guideline framework (D4.6 "Living Lab guidelines (final version)") are relevant to and adopted by the living lab community.

¹ <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/13/2/614>

1 Introduction

1.1 The VITALISE Project

Researchers in the Health and Wellbeing domain need 1) convenient access to research infrastructures, 2) direct engagement of people to validate hypotheses, co-design solutions and services, evaluate their feasibility and effectiveness and participate in the translation and mobilization of outcomes and 3) experience from multidisciplinary domains (e.g., healthcare management, assistive technologies, data science) to deal with the complexity of health and wellbeing research.

Over the last few years, Living Labs have emerged as resilient research and innovation infrastructures and have proved to be key to the integration of research and innovation processes in real life settings, focusing primarily on people and their engagement in research procedures. VITALISE opens Living Lab Infrastructures to facilitate and promote research activities in the Health and Wellbeing domain in Europe and beyond by enabling in person Transnational Access to 17 Living Lab research infrastructures and by supporting remote digital access to datasets (Virtual Access) of rehabilitation, transitional care and everyday life activities through harmonized processes and common tools. VITALISE will design and develop ICT tools for shared access of similar devices and applications used across Living Labs, as well as for collecting, storing, and sharing datasets. Lastly, VITALISE will invest in the development of Training methods towards the wider understanding and valorisation of Living Lab methodologies in the research community.

1.2 Description of WP4

Work Package 4 (WP4), "Capacity Building and training" is a central WP for the Vitalise project focusing on the creation of knowledge materials to support researchers and new living labs.

Some of the main tasks are the organization of summer schools, webinars, and training programmes, to support the design of university courses that will educate potential new researchers for the living lab research value & potential and to produce required materials for training and education.

1.3 Purpose of the document

This document aims to present a first version of a guideline framework for living labs to reach a (higher) level of harmonization. An updated version of this framework will be presented within deliverable D4.6 "Living Lab Guidelines (final version)".

This deliverable is part of Task 4.2 "Online educational material and training programmes", focusing on the dissemination of the living lab potential to new living labs and researchers. It will include information on methodologies and needed steps for setting up and harmonizing living labs.

This deliverable is linked with deliverable D2.2 "Evaluation process & tools" and with deliverable "D2.5 Standard version 4" and will be updated based on the later versions of the Standard, namely "D2.6 Standard version 5" and "D2.7 Standard version 6".

The purpose of this document is to identify the necessary steps which need to be part of the guideline framework for (new) living labs to increase their level of harmonization with other living labs. It provides definitions for each of the identified steps and describes what needs to be achieved before going forward to the next steps.

More in-depth guidelines for every step will be included in deliverable D4.6 "Living Lab Guidelines (final version)". Therefore, each of the steps will be further detailed within deliverable D4.6 "Living Lab Guidelines (final version)".

This document describes the main outcomes of the desktop research, focusing on necessary steps to be included into the guideline framework. More in-depth guidelines for every step will be included in deliverable D4.6 "Living Lab Guidelines (final version)". Therefore, each of the steps will be further detailed within deliverable D4.6 "Living Lab Guidelines (final version)".

The final guideline framework (together with the standardized structure and KPIs) will also support the development of a self-assessment tool which is scheduled for within task T2.3 "Establishment of evaluation process and tools".

1.4 Document structure

The deliverable is structured as such:

- **Section 1** (this section) provides information regarding the VITALISE project, aspects related to it, and the purpose of this document.
- **Section 2** discusses the scoping of the guideline framework, the desktop research and the work done within task 2.3 "Establishment of evaluation process and tools".
- **Section 3** describes each of the identified steps from the guideline framework.
- **Section 4** presents the plan of action for the further development of the guideline framework.
- **Section 5** provides some concluding remarks on this deliverable.

2 Guideline framework

2.1 Scoping the guideline framework

As mentioned by Kalinauskaitė & all (2021)², there is an **evident need for validated frameworks accompanied by practical guidelines** on how to set up and implement transdisciplinary collaboration initiatives in complex socio-ecological contexts, such as living labs.

Therefore, a guideline framework for helping living labs to reach a higher level of harmonization should be approached in a holistic way to cover all the possible maturity levels of new and existing living labs. Next to this the framework should also serve as a solid base for organizations considering starting a living lab.

Responding to that evident need, this guideline framework will include the necessary steps to start a living lab from scratch, since harmonizing the infrastructures, projects, processes, skills, methods & tools of living labs begins with setting up a living lab from the start.

The scoping of the guideline framework is based on desktop research around living lab guidelines to increase the harmonization of living labs, together with the work done within Task 2.3 "Establishment of evaluation process and tools".

The visualization here below provides an overview of all the performed steps so far within these two tracks:

Figure 1 Visualization performed steps (methodology over all)

² <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/13/2/614>

2.2 Desktop research guideline framework

2.2.1 Methodology

Desktop research was performed to identify existing knowledge around the creation of a guideline framework for living labs. Next to academic input, grey literature from living lab networks and projects including living labs was considered.

We used Google, Google scholar, ResearchGate and Academia.eu to search for following keywords:

- Guidelines & living labs.
- "How to set up a living lab"
- Harmonization & living labs.

Based on this desktop research, following resources were considered:

- 24 academic papers
- 14 (project) handbooks
- 5 other online sources (e.g., online courses, application flow).

An index of the identified resources can be found as Appendix 1 of this deliverable.

This document describes the main outcomes of this desktop research, focusing on necessary steps to be included into the guideline framework.

2.2.2 Results from the desktop research

First and foremost, the research shows that **only few examples of existing guideline frameworks for living labs are available** for the moment. Some examples of project handbooks providing information about steps on how to set up and/or run living lab are:

- LOOPER Guidelines for living labs³
- Mindb4ACT Living Lab guide⁴
- REWAISE Living Lab Methodology and online handbook⁵
- UNALAB Living Lab handbook⁶

In 2015, a so-called 3-layered model⁷ of a living lab was introduced by Schuurman to 'frame' the different levels of a living lab, which is widely adopted within the European Network of Living Labs⁸, world's biggest living lab network. This model exists out of 3 levels:

- Macro-level: the living lab constellation
- Meso-level: the living lab innovation projects
- Micro-level: the living lab methodology

³ http://looperproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/08/LOOPER_D4.1_Guidelines-for-Living-Labs_FINAL.pdf

⁴ https://livinglabing.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/Living-Lab-Guide_web.pdf

⁵ <http://rewise.eu/living-labs/>

⁶ <https://unalab.eu/system/files/2020-07/living-lab-handbook2020-07-09.pdf>

⁷ <https://biblio.ugent.be/publication/5931264>

⁸ <https://enoll.org/>

Figure 2 The 3-layered model introduced by Schuurman (2015) (Rewaise handbook)

However, our research showed that the existing frameworks focus mainly on the set up of the meso-level of a living lab and very little provide comprehensive information about the macro-level of a living lab.

Next to this, analysis also indicates that **a harmonized definition** about living labs is crucial to start from and efforts to reach that harmonized definition are still needed (see 3.1 Understanding the living lab concepts). The most adopted definition found is the one provided by ENoLL (European Network of Living Labs) on their website⁹:

*Living Labs (LLs) are open innovation ecosystems in **real-life environments** using **iterative feedback processes** throughout a **lifecycle approach** of an innovation to create **sustainable impact**.*

*They focus on **co-creation, rapid prototyping & testing**, and **scaling-up** innovations & businesses, providing (different types of) **joint-value** to the involved stakeholders.*

*In this context, living labs operate as **intermediaries/orchestrators** among citizens, research organizations, companies, and government agencies/levels.*

Within a wide variety of living labs, they all have common characteristics, but multiple different implementations.

In addition to this, analysis demonstrates **different designations concerning the key elements of a living lab**. In section 3.1 Understanding the living lab concepts, a more elaborative explanation about the key elements is included.

Considering the frequency of use, table 1 here below shows the most mentioned elements from the desktop research.

⁹ <https://enoll.org/about-us/what-are-living-labs/>

Table 1 Frequency of use terms key elements of a living lab

Key element	Frequency of use
Stakeholders & users (people)	10
Governance	9
Infrastructure	8
Strategy (objectives)	7
(Multi-) methods & tools	6
Active user-involvement	5
Real-life context	5
Sustainability (business model)	5
Openness	4
Value (outcomes/impact)	4
Testing & experimentation	4
Co-creation	3
Communication	2
Evaluation	1
Service creation	1

Furthermore, the **interaction and collaboration with other living labs** proves to be a crucial aspect in the long-term success (sustainability) of living labs (Feurstein & all, 2008; Schuurman & all, 2013; Santonen & all, 2020; Alonso Raposo & all, 2021). More information about this can be found in section 3.8 *Achieve sustainability*.

On top of this, **the harmonization of different aspects** (e.g., methods & tools, infrastructures) **of the living labs** is mentioned multiple times by different authors as a driver for growth (Mulder & all, 2007; Feurstein & all, 2008; Schuurman & all, 2013; Santonen & all, 2020; Alonso Raposo & all, 2021). *More information about this can be found in section 3.9 Using/developing harmonized infrastructures, processes, standards, methods & tools.*

Analysis of all the different resources from the desktop research shows that the process of reaching harmonization as a living lab (including macro-meso-micro level) can be divided into **3 chronological phases**:

1. **The onboarding phase** includes the steps on how to understand the living lab concept and how to set-up a living lab.
2. **The running phase** includes the steps on how to run a living lab and how to grow experiences.
3. **The harmonization phase** includes the steps on how to become a sustainable living lab and how to harmonize infrastructures, projects, processes, skills, methods & tools.

In general, multiple authors mention **the importance of the onboarding phase** in general and the **governance** (across the 3 chronological phases) of the living lab more specifically (Kviselius & all, 2008; den Ouden & all, 2016; Sarrabi & all, 2021; Alonso Raposo & all, 2021). *More information about this can be found in section 3.3 Set up the living lab.*

2.3 Establishment of evaluation process and tools

To further support the desktop research around guidelines for living labs, we included the work done within Task 2.3 "Establishment of evaluation process and tools" in which KPI's for the set up and maturity of living labs are being defined, including a specific section on harmonization.

2.3.1 Objectives

The adoption of a standardized structure to evaluate living labs, considering all three levels of a Living Lab (macro-meso-micro) (Schuurman, 2015), will support the evaluation and assessment of all diverse types of living labs to help them becoming more impactful & sustainable.

Living lab literature shows that currently such a **standardized framework is lacking** although many different authors (Mulder & all, 2007; Salminen & all, 2011; Ståhlbröst, 2012; Mastelic, 2015; Van Geenhuizen, 2018; Santonen, 2018; Bronson & all, 2021; Dekker & all, 2021; Vervoort & all, 2022...) indicate the importance of such an evaluation approach.

Considering that evaluation frameworks serve as well the purpose of giving deeper insights into quality assessment and most essential improvements, identify strengths and weaknesses, identify areas in which support and cooperation are needed, evaluate progress, when previous evaluation data is available and identify barriers and development needs, LL (Living Labs) **evaluation frameworks should be considered an accelerator for deepening the understanding of the LL architectures and individual LL members.**

Evaluation frameworks that are not adequately structured potentially constrain the development of a sustainable living lab movement and hamper the possibility to work at the right architectural level for building a sustainable, impactful, and effective living lab structure.

2.3.2 Purpose of the evaluation framework

The aim is to create an evaluation framework which can be used for all diverse types of living labs around the globe, no matter which sector(s) they are active in. However, translations to more sector specific KPIs to contextualize their living labs better should remain possible. The framework will include clear definitions, scoring tables and KPIs for measuring the maturity of living labs.

A KPI (Key Performance Indicators) is a measure (whether quantitative or qualitative) to review the progress compared to its objectives. It is used to measure performance over time and to compare results with other living lab organizations.

Next to this, the standardized framework will provide support for:

- *a self-assessment tool for living labs to measure their maturity.*
- *expert evaluations of living labs (within projects).*
- *benchmarks of living labs cross-border and cross-sectoral, but equally within a specific sector and/or a specific region.*

The framework, which is further developed within this process, is the one as published within the academic paper '*Harmonizing the evaluation of living labs: a standardized evaluation framework*' (Vervoort & all, 2022)¹⁰, part of WP2 of the Vitalise project.

The standardized structure exists out of 6 chapters and 15 criteria as shown here below:

¹⁰ https://www.academia.edu/81060356/Harmonizing_the_evaluation_of_living_labs_a_standardized_evaluation_framework

Figure 3 Standardized evaluation framework: chapters and criteria. (Vervoort & all,2021)

Based on this structure clear descriptions for each criterion are developed, together with a list of KPIs to measure these criteria.

In a next phase of the development (see 4. Next steps), the outcomes will be used to:

1. create scoring tables for each criterion to benchmark the maturity of living labs regarding that specific criterion.
2. determine the necessary formulas to calculate that maturity correctly.
3. design the evaluation methods to collect the data from living labs.
4. support the development of a self-assessment tool, based on these previous steps.

2.3.3 Methodology

To validate the description sentences of each criterion and to define the necessary KPIs, a multi-method approach was applied.

First, an extensive literature review (see 2.3.4.1) was executed to collect input from the academic world around the evaluation and maturity of living labs to identify relevant existing definitions and KPIs. Therefore, this literature review was different as the one part of the desktop research on living lab guidelines (see 2.2.1)

In addition to this, a desktop review concerning definitions and KPIs from current and past projects from ENoLL was made, together with a review of KPIs and definitions used by other (living lab) networks and/or external organizations assessing living labs.

Simultaneously, an online survey (n=24) investigated the necessary description sentences, targeting living lab practitioners and experts. Offering them the opportunity to comment (n=16) on the proposals made within Task 2.3 "Establishment evaluation process & tools".

The literature review, the input from ENoLL projects and from external organizations resulted in 3 large excel files indexing the outcomes chapter by chapter and criterion by criterion. After the collection of all this data, the indexed results were compared and clustered (see appendix 4). Based on this a description sentence overview (see 2.3.4.5) and a KPI table (see 2.3.4.6) were defined.

Next to this a macro-meso-micro table of KPIs was created to show the relationship of each KPI to the three different levels of a living lab.

Currently, the descriptions sentences and the KPI table are being validated:

- Internally via the partners of Work Package 2 and the Vitalise Pilot group, existing out of living lab members of Vitalise, Forum LLSA & ENoLL.
- Externally via academic living lab experts (identified within the literature review) during an online workshop and the ENoLL Labelling task force, which has a large expertise on measuring the maturity of living labs.

Following this approach will safeguard the outcomes being relevant to and adopted by the living lab community.

2.3.4 Outcomes

2.3.4.1 Literature review

To collect input from the academic world around the evaluation and maturity of living labs a literature review was executed via:

- Academia.eu
- Google scholar
- Researchgate.net
- internal ENoLL paper archives

To achieve a correct outcome, aligning with the chapters and the criteria of the standardized framework (Vervoort & all, 2022), following search terms (always in combination with the term living labs) were used in the scoping of the papers to be included, starting with the general search terms KPIs, evaluation & maturity before continuing with the terms from every chapter and criteria of the framework:

- KPIs
- Evaluation
- Maturity
- Strategy
- Governance
- Business model
- Culture
- Operations
- Human Resources
- Equipment
- Infrastructure(s)
- Innovation process
- Innovation partnerships
- Ownership of results

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- Users & reality
- Iterative process
- Real-life settings
- User centricity
- Participatory tools & methods
- (Co-created) values
- Impact(s)
- Stability
- Sustainability
- Scale-up
- Harmonization

All identified papers were indexed in an Excel overview including following columns:

- title of the paper
- author(s)
- year of publication
- link to the search terms

This step resulted in 175 indexed papers.

Following this, we read all included abstracts to determine the final list for this literature review. For this we used the traffic light principle using colors in the index to indicate which papers will be:

- read into depth (green colored) to identify essential KPIs for the evaluation framework.
- scanned thoroughly (orange colored) to add (sector specific) KPIs.
- excluded (red colored) from further reading based on the analysis of their abstracts.

This step resulted in:

- 60 green-colored papers which were read in depth.
- 59 orange-colored papers which will be scanned thoroughly.
- 56 red-colored and excluded papers.

After having read the green colored papers, 38 of them provided valuable insights for our evaluation framework, its descriptions and necessary KPIs, while 22 others seemed less relevant to refine our framework.

The orange-colored papers will be used to refine KPIs within specific sectors. The results of this work will be reported in D4.6 Living Lab guidelines final version.

All the outcomes of this step were indexed in an excel overview to be compared and matched with the inputs from the desktop research of the ENoLL projects and the inputs from the other assessment frameworks.

2.3.4.2 ENoLL projects

Next to this literature review, a review was made concerning included KPIs and definitions within all past and present ENoLL projects.

After investigation of all past and current ENoLL projects, following items were identified as useful for the KPI table:

1. iSCAPE_D5.5_cross-evaluation_CoChairs.v2.0¹¹
2. SISCODE assessment report D3.5¹²
3. Draft evaluation framework SCORE (Smart Control Of the climate Resilience in European)
4. OPEN Lab evaluation framework
5. Vitalise auto evaluation v2.2
6. Rewaise Handbook¹³
7. Soil mission implementation plan final

All the outcomes of this step were indexed in an excel overview to be compared and matched with the inputs from the literature review and the inputs from the other assessment frameworks.

¹¹ https://www.iscapeproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/iSCAPE-D5.5_Final.pdf

¹² https://siscodproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/SISCODE_D3.5_Assessment-report_small.pdf

¹³ http://rewaise.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/05/REWAISE-LL-online_handbook.pdf

2.3.4.3 Other assessment frameworks

As a last step in the collection of KPIs and definitions we looked at the KPIs used by other (living lab) networks and/or external organizations to assess living labs.

After desktop research following frameworks could be discovered:

1. Living Lab Markers¹⁴ (WeLL, Institute Godin, Smart gastronomy lab...)
2. Self-assessment Forum LLSA¹⁵
3. Water-oriented living labs manual¹⁶ (Water Europe)
4. ProVaHealth self-assessment tool¹⁷
5. SCIROCCO exchange maturity model¹⁸
6. Super MoRRI Self-assessment tool¹⁹
7. B-Water Smart indicators²⁰
8. CoAct-Self assessment template²¹
9. ECSA ten principles of Citizen Science²²
10. C3Places Methodological framework for living labs²³
11. EIT Urban Mobility tool²⁴
12. ENERGISE Living Lab evaluation and assessment manual²⁵
13. MOVE 21 Impact assessment framework for living labs²⁶

All the outcomes of this step were indexed in an excel overview to be compared and matched with the inputs from the literature review and the inputs from the ENoLL projects.

2.3.4.4 Survey criteria descriptions

During March 2023 living lab practitioners and experts were invited to participate in an online survey around the KPI sentences for a living lab evaluation framework.

This survey was hosted via Microsoft forms and proposed for each of the criteria of the standardized structure two description sentences, based on the input of the online workshops held with the Vitalise pilot group in 2022, where they could choose from.

For each of the criteria they also had the opportunity to comment on the proposed sentences.

Figure 4 Screenshot Microsoft form online survey criteria descriptions living lab experts and practitioners.

¹⁴ <https://www.marqueurs-livinglab.org/?lang=en>

¹⁵ <https://www.forumllsa.org/>

¹⁶ https://watereurope.eu/wp-content/uploads/WoLL-Notebook-Series2_2pages.pdf

¹⁷ <https://scanbalt.org/toolbox/survey/>

¹⁸ <https://www.sciroccoexchange.com/uploads/SCIROCCO-Exchange-Maturity-Model-v1.0-13.06.2019.pdf>

¹⁹ <https://super-morri.eu/findings/>

²⁰ <https://b-watersmart.eu/results-downloads/>

²¹ <https://coactproject.eu/toolkit/method/self-assessment-survey-for-citizen-social-science-projects/>

²² ECSA (European Citizen Science Association). 2015. Ten principles of citizen science. Berlin. <http://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/XPR2N>

²³ https://c3places.eu/sites/default/files/page-files/C3Places_D1_1%20Methodological%20Framework%20for%20LIVING%20LABS.pdf

²⁴ <https://livinglabs.eitum.eu/tools/>

²⁵ https://energise-project.eu/sites/default/files/content/ENERGISE_D3.5_230218_Final_0.pdf

²⁶ https://move21.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/MOVE21-WP8-D8.1-Impact-Assessment-Framework-for-Living-Labs_compressed.pdf

A total of 24 experts and practitioners participated in the survey providing valuable insights to make the necessary iterations to result in a final proposal of criteria descriptions to be validated by internal and external key stakeholders (see 2.3.3 Methodology). Their input was integrated, together with the inputs from the literature review and desktop research into the criteria sentences overview (see 2.3.4.5)

A full overview of the online survey is added as Appendix 2 to this deliverable.

2.3.4.5 Overview updated framework and criteria sentences.

Comparing the input of the living lab experts and practitioners (n=24) with the literature review and desktop research a few adaptations were adopted to the standardized framework (Vervoort & all, 2022, see Figure 3) based on the insights from the survey and the literature & desktop review:

- *the criterion 'Culture' was renamed into 'Culture & collaboration'.*
- *the criterion 'Innovation processes & partnerships' was renamed into 'Innovation partnerships, projects & processes'.*
- *the sub criterion 'Project culture' was renamed into 'Innovation culture'.*
- *the sub criterion 'Partner agreements' was moved to the Governance part of the framework.*
- *The sub criterion 'Academic validation' was moved to the Impacts part of the framework.*
- *the sub criterion 'Business plan' was renamed into 'Foresight'.*
- *the sub criterion 'Cross-border/cross-sectoral' was renamed into 'Scalability'.*
- *the sub criterion 'Standardization' was renamed into 'Harmonization'.*
- *the sub criterion 'Benchmarking knowledge transfer & capacity building' was renamed into 'Benchmarking'.*

As a result, Table 2 here below shows the iterated standardized framework which exists out of 6 chapters, 15 criteria, and 55 sub criteria.

Table 2 Iterated standardized evaluation framework (chapters, criteria & subcriteria)

Chapter	Criterion	Sub Criterion
Strategy	Governance	1. Involvement Q4/Q5 actors
		2. Shared vision & mission
		3. Participative approach/open governance
		4. Partner agreements
		5. Expected impacts, strategy & projects
		6. Team design
	Business Model	7. Service portfolio
		8. Stakeholder/contributor partnerships
		9. Status of the organization
		10. Financial engineering
	Culture & Collaboration	11. Internal communication strategy
		12. Internal collaboration strategy
		13. External collaboration strategy
		14. Innovation culture
		15. Availability & assignment

Operations	Human Resources	16. Role fluidity
	Operations	17. Experiences projects & activities
		18. Monitoring processes
		19. Branding & positioning
	Equipment & infrastructure	20. Availability
21. Access		
Openness	Innovation partnerships, projects & processes	22. Transparency level
		23. Openness partnerships
	Ownership of results	24. Data agreements
		25. Types of ownership
		26. IP processes
27. Feedback protection		
Users & reality	User centricity	28. Representativity
		29. Permanence user panel
		30. Intensity
	Lifecycle & real-life	31. Lifecycle/iterative process
		32. Real-life settings
	Tools & methods	33. Engagement strategies
		34. Range tools & methods
		35. External communication strategy
36. Quality/innovativeness		
Impact & value	Co-created values	37. User satisfaction
		38. Stakeholder satisfaction
		39. Knowledge sharing
		40. Capacity building
		41. Value capturing strategies
		42. Value chain coverage
	Impacts	43. Societal impact
		44. Environmental impact
		45. Economic impact
		46. Regulatory impact

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Stability & harmonization		47. Internal impact
		48. Academic validation
	Stability	49. Improved collaborations
		50. SWOT
		51. Foresight
	Harmonization & scale-up	52. Replicability
		53. Scalability
		54. Harmonization
55. Benchmarking		

Next to this the proposed sentences for each of the criteria were iterated (if applicable) one last time. These sentences will be validated again internally (VITALISE pilot group) and externally (ENoLL labelling task force & academic living lab experts).

The final outcomes will be reported within D4.6 'Living Lab Guidelines final version'. Table 3, here below, shows the overview of the iterated sentences of each criterion.

Table 3 Overview criterion descriptions

Chapter	Criterion	Description
Strategy	Governance	<i>The Living Lab governance is SMART (specific, measurable, acceptable, realistic, time-bound) if it includes all the major actors of the quadruple/quintuple helix, along with a systematic participative approach (rules & processes), a shared vision and mission which can impact the Living Lab strategy and the projects for better outcomes, and a clear Team Management (a clear definition of each actor roles).</i>
	Business Model	<i>A sustainable living lab business model enables the living lab to strengthen its status & service portfolio via active stakeholder partnerships & financial engineering.</i>
	Culture & collaboration	<i>The culture of a living lab empowers internal collaboration & communication strategies and strengthens external collaborations, within an open & solid innovation culture.</i>
Operations	Human Resources	<i>The living lab has clearly defined internal roles (e.g., living lab manager, panel manager...) and assigned people to these roles in a flexible & sufficient way based on competences required & skills available.</i>
	Operations	<i>The living lab shows experience in executing monitored projects and activities, within the scope of their branding (positioning).</i>
	Equipment & infrastructure	<i>The living lab has sufficient access to the equipment (hard- & software) & infrastructure (facilities, networks) they need to run their living lab and its main activities in an easy, stable & structured way.</i>
Openness	Innovation partnerships, projects & processes	<i>The living lab has a transparent way of dealing with open innovation partnerships, projects & processes.</i>
	Ownership of results	<i>The living lab has monitored & transparent processes & agreements to protect stakeholders' feedback and deal with property rights (IPR).</i>
Users & reality	User centricity	<i>A user-centric living lab has an active (long-term) group of users that represents the ecosystem of the living lab, influencing the innovation processes.</i>

	Lifecycle & real-life	<i>The living lab actively engages & involves users in every phase of the innovation process/project within realistic real-life settings of the users.</i>
	Tools & methods	<i>The living lab has strong engagement strategies, supported by transparent & tailored communication processes, using a range of tools & methods relevant to specific phases of the innovation cycle.</i>
Impact & Value	Co-created values	<i>The living lab co-creates values for all their different types of stakeholders (including users) from their value chain by sharing knowledge and building capacities of their stakeholders.</i>
	Impacts	<i>Based on their strategies the living lab creates (long-term) impacts within one or more of following aspects of their ecosystem: societal, environmental, economic, regulatory, academical, while improving their operational excellence.</i>
Stability & harmonization	Stability	<i>The stability of a living lab is enhanced by strong relationships with partners & customers, the development of value propositions and a mature, balanced & diversified set of funding & revenue streams.</i>
	Harmonization & scale-up	<i>The Living Lab has the ability replicate and scale-up products, solutions (including infrastructures) & services by transferring, benchmarking & harmonizing knowledge, skills, standards, methods, tools & processes to a wider network of relevant (cross-border/cross-sectoral) actors.</i>

These sentences offer valuable insights into the essential steps of the guideline framework. They not only highlight the key elements of a living lab (as discussed in section 3.1, "Understanding the living lab concepts"), but they also provide an overview of the process to achieve harmonization across the three identified phases: onboarding, running, and harmonization (as outlined in section 2.2.2, "Results of desktop research").

2.3.4.6 Overview of the KPI table

The next step was to determine a list of general living lab KPIs, based on the analysis of:

- the 60 green-colored papers selected (see 2.3.4.1 Literature review)
- the 7 selected ENoLL projects (see 2.3.4.2 ENoLL projects)
- the 13 external frameworks (see 2.3.4.3 Other assessment frameworks)

A comparison of these 3 types of resources resulted in a prioritized longlist of inputs on important aspects for each chapter and criterion.

Appendix 3 is offering an overview of this prioritized longlist, along with the respective authors/resources that contributed to each item.

This longlist resulted in a clustered final selection of 50 general living lab KPIs, based on the frequency/importance mentioned for each KPI within the longlist (Appendix 3).

These KPIs will be further validated again internally (Vitalise pilot group) and externally (ENoLL labelling task force and academic living lab experts).

The KPIs are divided over the 6 chapters and 15 criteria of the standardized framework and will, together with the criteria description sentences (see 2.3.4.5), support the development of:

- the necessary scoring tables for each criterion measuring the maturity of living labs on these specific aspects of a living lab to reach a higher level of harmonization,
- the checklists within every step of the first version of the guideline framework of this deliverable by providing quantitative inputs to assess the maturity of living labs,
- the set-up of a self-assessment tool within Task 2.3 'Evaluation process & tools'.

The clustered selection of 50 KPIs in relation to the standardized framework are presented in Table 4, here below.

Within the next steps (see 4 Next steps), for each Criterion (& KPIs if relevant) a scoring table will be created from 0 to 5 to benchmark the maturity of the living lab in relation to that specific criterion.

Table 4 KPI table

Chapter	Criterion	KPI
Strategy	Governance	1. % of involvement of different stakeholders in the vision/mission (e.g., all Q4/5 represented is 100%)
		2. % of involvement of different stakeholders in the governance, supported by the necessary partner agreements (including clear actor roles)
		3. Presence of SMART goals and decision-making processes (responsibilities)
	Business Model	4. Presence of a business model (canvas), including customers, value proposition, resources, revenues, and costs (e.g., LIAISON)
		5. Presence of a service portfolio covering (all) phases of the lifecycle approach
		6. Presence of partner agreements/arrangement for co-innovation
		7. % Who's paying/contributing with what (private & public funding, revenues service portfolio)
	Culture & Collaboration	8. Internal & external relation management process/strategy in place (including client contracts)
		9. Frequency of internal communication & results sharing
		10. Number of regional, national & international (long-term) collaborations
Operations	Human Resources	11. Implementation of clear internal roles and responsibilities
		12. Amount of qualified (internal/external) staff (Full-Time-Equivalent)
		13. % of Role flexibility within the organization (i.e., how many (different/multiple) people can execute (different/multiple) roles)
	Operations	14. Number of (finished) living lab projects and/or activities/ 3 year
		15. Quality of internal monitoring framework (strategic, financial, equipment & infrastructure, policy, project outcomes)
		16. Frequency of monitoring the living lab and its main activities
	Equipment & infrastructure	17. Presence of facilities
		18. Presence of hard- and software
		19. % of time availability of equipment and infrastructure to the living lab
Openness	Innovation partnerships, projects & processes	20. Level of reflective & iterative approach to transdisciplinary collaboration
		21. Transparency of project roles, selection & execution (including accessible and understandable information)
		22. Presence of an ethical approach (e.g., regulatory requirements, data protection needed)
	Ownership of results	23. Presence of strategy & processes for ownership of the rights & profits (including data) of collaborative outcomes

		24. Presence of rules & regulations regarding the use, sharing & licensing of intellectual property (prior to the project)
		25. Presence of user agreements (data, intellectual property, rights, liabilities)
Users & reality	User centricity	26. Diversity of profiled end users
		27. (% of the) Role of end users according to the levels of involvement
		28. Level of permanence of the user panel beyond living lab projects
	Lifecycle & real-life	29. Number of users involved in the different phases of the innovation cycle
		30. Concreteness of real-life settings enabling users to participate in their natural environments
		31. % of time of user involvement within real-life settings
	Tools & methods	32. Proof of a structured & transparent approach/strategy for active user involvement throughout the innovation cycle
		33. Range tools & methods for the different phases of the innovation cycle
		34. Proof of a transparent (concept, background, process, outcomes & results) communication approach/strategy tailored to the different types of stakeholders
Impact & value	Co-created values	35. % Satisfaction of users/stakeholders (from the whole value chain) concerning their involvement/influence
		36. Frequency of knowledge sharing (including results) with relevant (internal & external) stakeholders from the value chain
		37. Number of (open) educational resources (including datasets) shared/provided for relevant stakeholders
		38. % Satisfaction of users/stakeholders concerning knowledge sharing & capacity building (learning materials & infrastructures)
	Impacts	39. Presence of an impact assessment framework & procedures
		40. Frequency of impact assessments
		41. % of improvement of organizational excellence (e.g., working procedures/processes, desired knowledge & skills)
Stability & harmonization	Stability	42. % Increase of relationships with a reliable partner network and customers
		43. Level of financial maturity based on a balanced & diversified set of funding & revenue streams
		44. Number of living lab value propositions, flexible to adapt to eventual new needs
	Harmonization & scale-up	45. % Increase of partners committed to scale up products/solutions/services
		46. Number of products/solutions/services (able to be) scaled-up
		47. % increase of influence on and/or collaboration with other (networks of) living labs

		48. Number of transferred living lab infrastructures, standards, skills, methods, tools, processes & services to other (networks) of living labs and/or relevant actors
		49. Number of adopted harmonized living lab infrastructures, standards, skills, methods, tools, processes & services
		50. Number of (cross-border/cross-sectoral) initiatives/projects based on common processes

To make sure diversification is possible between different types of living labs concerning the created impacts they are aspiring, 11 more KPIs were distilled to cover the 5 different impact clusters (see 2.3.4.5): societal, environmental, economic, regulatory, and academic.

Societal

1. % positive increase in changing mindsets, behavioral modification and/or well-being of relevant stakeholders/users
2. number of implemented solutions responding to local challenges & opportunities

Environmental

3. % increase awareness environmental issues addressed by the living lab
4. % positive increase of use of (natural) resources

Economic

5. Number of new business created/supported (e.g., spin-offs/start-ups)
6. Number of patents/licenses awarded
7. % of reduced development risks & costs

Regulatory

8. Number of adapted/implemented policies and/or directives
9. % increase of common understanding/dialogue between political representatives & the (innovation) ecosystem)

Academical

10. Number of scientific papers and/or publications/articles
11. Number of awarded and/or highly referred publications

2.3.4.7 Macro-meso-micro table

The next step of the process of developing a standardized framework for evaluation of living labs and their maturity was to verify if the selected KPIs are offering a solution to the problem statement (see 2.3.1) posed about the lack of a standardized structure to evaluate living labs, considering all three levels of a Living Lab. Therefore, we matched every KPI (see 2.3.4.6) with the identified 3 levels of a living lab to check their compliance to each of them.

As a result of this matching exercise, we learn that:

- 44 out of 50 KPIs are related to the macro-level of a living lab.
- 37 out of 50 KPIs are related to the meso-level of a living lab.
- 24 out of 50 KPIs are related to the micro-level of a living lab.
- 17 out of 50 KPIs are related to all levels of a living lab.
- Therefore, it can be concluded that the 50 KPIs are covering all three levels of a living lab properly.

Figure 4 shows the relationship of every KPI to the macro-, meso- and micro-level of a living lab.

This proposed macro-meso-micro table still needs to be validated internally (Vitalise pilot group and harmonization board) and externally (ENoLL labelling task force and living lab experts). The final version of this table will be presented in Deliverable 4.6.

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	44	37	24
	Macro	Meso	Micro
Strategy			
Governance			
% of involvement in the vision/mission of stakeholders	1		
% of involvement in the governance of stakeholders, supported by the necessary partner agreements (including clear actor roles)	1		
presence of SMART goals and decision-making processes (responsibilities)	1	1	
Business Model			
presence of a business model canvas, including customers, value proposition, resources, revenues, and costs (e.g., LIABILITY)	1	1	
presence of a service portfolio covering (all) phases of the lifecycle approach	1	1	
presence of partner agreements/arrangement for co-innovation	1	1	
% Who's paying/contributing with what (private & public funding, revenues service portfolio)	1	1	
Culture & collaboration			
internal and external relation management process/strategy in place (including client contracts)	1	1	
frequency of internal communication & results sharing	1	1	1
number of regional, national & international (long-term) collaborations	1		
Operations			
Human Resources			
implementation of clear internal roles and responsibilities	1	1	1
amount of qualified (internal/external) staff (FTE)	1		
% of role flexibility (i.e. (different/multiple) people can execute (different/multiple) roles)	1	1	1
Operations			
number of (finished) living lab projects and/or activities	1	1	1
quality of internal monitoring framework (strategic, financial, E&I, policy, project outcomes)	1		
frequency of monitoring the living lab and its main activities	1		
Equipment & infrastructure			
presence of facilities	1	1	
presence of hard- and software	1	1	
% time availability of E&I to the living lab	1		
Openness			
Innovation partnerships, projects & processes			
level of reflective and iterative approach to transdisciplinary collaboration	1	1	1
transparency of project roles, selection & execution (including accessible and understandable information)		1	
presence of an ethical approach (e.g., regulatory requirements, data protection needed etc.)	1	1	1
Ownership of results			
presence of strategy & processes for ownership of the rights & profits (including data) of collaborative outcomes	1	1	1
presence of rules & regulations regarding the use, sharing & licensing of IP (prior to the project)	1	1	1
presence of user agreements in place (data, IPR, rights, liabilities)	1	1	1

Figure 5 Macro-meso-micro KPI Table

2.3.4.8 Living Lab lexicon

As a last step of the work done so far within Task 2.3 'Evaluation processes and tools', a list of key words was deduced from the updated evaluation framework, the criteria descriptions and the KPIs. This list will help the further development of the Living Lab lexicon within WP2 Harmonization activities (reported in D2.5 Standard Version 4)

General

- macro level of a living lab
- meso level of a living lab
- micro level of a living lab

Strategy

- Governance
 - governance model
 - governance
 - decision-making processes
 - quadruple helix
 - participative approach (rules & processes)
 - partner agreements
 - shared vision
 - shared mission
 - actor roles (e.g., enabler)
- Business model
 - business model

- value proposition
- service portfolio
- stakeholder partnerships
- financial engineering

- Culture & collaboration
 - internal collaboration
 - communication strategies
 - innovation culture

Operations

- Human resources
 - internal living lab roles (e.g., living lab manager, panel manager)
- Operations
 - living lab project
 - living lab activity
 - internal living lab monitoring framework
- Equipment & infrastructure
 - living lab equipment
 - living lab infrastructures

Openness

- Innovation partnerships, projects & processes
 - *innovation partnerships*
 - *transdisciplinary collaboration*
- Ownership of results
 - *IPR*
 - *feedback protection*

User & reality

- User centricity
 - *living lab users*
 - *living lab stakeholders*
 - *active user involvement*
 - *representativity/diversity*
 - *levels of engagement (e.g., inform, consult...)*
 - *user panel permanence*
- Lifecycle & real-life
 - *innovation lifecycle*
 - *integrative process*
 - *iterative approach*
 - *real-life settings*
- Tools & methods
 - *engagement strategies*
 - *tailored communication processes*
 - *range of methods & tools*

Impact & value

- Co-created values
 - *co-created values*
 - *value chain*
 - *knowledge sharing*
 - *capacity building*
- Impacts
 - *operational excellence*
 - *societal impact of a living lab*
 - *environmental impact of a living lab*
 - *economic impact of a living lab*
 - *regulatory impact of a living lab*
 - *academic validation*
 - *tangible & intangible outcomes*
 - *impact assessment framework*
 - *behavioural modification*

Stability & harmonization

- Stability
 - *foresight*
 - *SWOT*
 - *partner network*
- Harmonization & scale-up
 - *replicability*
 - *scalability*
 - *scale-up*
 - *knowledge transfer*
 - *benchmarking*

3 The guideline framework

The guideline framework for living labs covers the three identified phases to reach harmonization as a living lab:

The onboarding phase includes the steps on how to understand the living lab concept and how to set-up a living lab.

The running phase includes the steps on how to run a living lab and how to grow experiences.

The harmonization phase includes the steps on how to become a sustainable living lab and how to harmonize infrastructures, projects, processes, skills, methods & tools.

In general, multiple authors mention **the importance of the onboarding phase** and the **governance** of the living lab more specifically (Kviselius & all, 2008; den Ouden & all, 2016; Sarrabi & all, 2021; Alonso Raposo & all, 2021).

The guideline framework exists out of 10 steps as shown here below. In the following chapter of this document, we describe each of these steps in detail.

Onboarding

1. Understand the living lab concepts.
2. Assess your living lab status.
3. Set up the living lab.

Running

4. Execute living lab projects & activities (gain experience).

5. Monitor your progress & impact.
6. Learn from others.

Harmonizing

7. Join thematic/geographical working groups & networks.
8. Achieve sustainability (financial, value propositions, skills & knowledge)
9. Using/developing harmonized infrastructures, processes, standards, methods & tools.
10. Collaborate in (cross-border/cross-sectoral) projects/networks based on harmonized infrastructures, processes, standards, methods & tools.

The section below present one by one the different steps of the framework.

3.1 Understand the Living Lab Concept

3.1.1 Definition of a living lab

Over the last decades many definitions of what a living lab is, have been proposed.

As Bergvall-Kåreborn and Ståhlbröst²⁷ already identified in 2009, in research and practice, living labs have been described as a methodology, an organization, a system, an arena, an environment, and a systemic innovation approach.

Our research confirms these insights from Bergvall-Kåreborn and Ståhlbröst since we found multiple different definitions of a living lab in research and practice:

In 2015, Cremers²⁸ describes it as '**a social practice around ill-defined, authentic tasks or issues whose resolution requires transboundary learning by transcending disciplines, traditional structures and sectors, and forms of learning**'.

Kalagasidis & all²⁹ call them '**instruments for advancing user-centered innovations in various areas of human activities**' back in 2017.

Wang & all³⁰ in 2018 see it as '**a typical indoor environment where everyday tasks are performed by occupants over a significant period of time**'.

In 2020, Santonen & all³¹, use the term '**an open innovation approach highlighting active user involvement, multi-stakeholder collaboration while conducting testing and development activities in real-life settings across the different innovation process stages**'.

Krassimira & Cooper³² (2021) define it as '**a practical tool for pursuing innovation**'.

In 2022, Zipfel & all³³ envision it as '**a research method to enhance participation of end- users in the development and implementation process of an innovation**'.

But also, in projects different definitions are used. Within the Agri link assessment tool they describe it as '**a multi-actor open innovation processes bringing together public and private users and stakeholders to co-create, validate, and test new services, business ideas, markets, and technologies in 'real-life' contexts**', while in the Lightsense living lab handbook they use '**spaces for the information and communication technology (ICT) society**'.

²⁷ Bergvall-Kåreborn, Birgitta & Ståhlbröst, Anna. (2009). *Living Lab: An Open and Citizen-Centric Approach for Innovation*.

²⁸ Cremers, P. (2015): *Guidebook living Labs: tool for designing and evaluating living labs at the interface between school and workplace*.

²⁹ Kalagasidis, A., Hagy, S., Marx, C. (2017). *The HSB Living Lab harmonization cube. Informes de la Construcción*.

³⁰ Wang, A., Change, F., Yousefi, S., Li, B., Campbell, B. and Heydarian, A. (2018). *The Hitchiker's Guide to Successful Living Lab Operations*.

³¹ Santonen, T.; Julin, M.; Salmi, A. & Leskinen, J. (2020) *Understanding the underlying factors of living lab business model*.

³² Krassimira P., Cooper I., (2021) *Are living labs effective? Exploring the evidence*.

³³ Zipfel N, Horreh B, Hulshof CTJ, et al. *The relationship between the living lab approach and successful implementation of healthcare innovations: an integrative review*.

Most of these different interpretations are only focusing on one specific aspect of a living lab and are therefore limited in their approach. In the next sub-section (3.1.2) we describe the 3-layered model which is offering a solution to this problem.

Despite all the different definitions we found, there is also one which is very regularly used within research and practice, being the one proposed by ENoLL on their website³⁴:

Living Labs (LLs) are open innovation ecosystems in real-life environments using iterative feedback processes throughout a lifecycle approach of an innovation to create sustainable impact.

*They focus on **co-creation, rapid prototyping & testing, and scaling-up** innovations & businesses, providing (different types of) **joint-value** to the involved stakeholders.*

*In this context, living labs operate as **intermediaries/orchestrators** among citizens, research organizations, companies, and government agencies/levels.*

Within a wide variety of living labs, they all have common characteristics, but multiple different implementations.

In the context of increasing harmonization, at this moment, we propose to **use the ENoLL definition as standard** for supporting this guideline framework. However, this definition will be also further discussed internally and externally to safeguard it still covers all different types of existing and emerging living labs. If necessary, an updated definition will be reported within D4.6 'Guidelines living labs final version.'

3.1.2 The 3 levels of a living lab

Aiming to solve this problem of different interpretations, Schuurman introduced in 2015 in his PhD Dissertation '*Bridging the gap between open and user innovation? Exploring the value of Living Labs as a means to structure user contribution and manage distributed innovation*'³⁵, the **3-layered model of a living lab** (see also 2.2.2).

He describes following levels:

- '*On a **macro level**, a living lab is a public-private-people partnership consisting of different stakeholders, organized to carry out Living Lab research and Living Lab projects. We propose the term **living lab constellation** to refer to this level.*'
- '*On the **meso level**, we discern the Living Lab innovation projects that are being carried out within the living lab constellation. We can also refer to this as **living lab projects**.*'
- '*The research activities that are deployed in a living lab project we propose to label as the **micro level** activities in Living Labs. Mostly, this consists of a **specific Living Lab methodology** to 'cultivate user-led insights' and 'surface tacit, experiential, and domain-based knowledge.'*'

Furthermore, he explains:

*'As we discussed in the previous chapter, Ståhlbröst (2012) noticed that some living labs exist where the living lab constellation is set-up for only one innovation project, which merges the macro and meso level, but as we saw in the previous chapter and as we will further argue in the next chapter, **we regard these 'Living Lab as a project' initiatives as problematic in terms of sustainability and sub-optimal in terms of added value being generated for the actors involved.***'

The work of Schuurman is in line with the work of Kviselius (2008)³⁶ on an analytical framework of the living lab open innovation levels as shown here below, indicating a strategic, functional, and operational level.

³⁴ <https://enoll.org/about-us/what-are-living-labs/>

³⁵ Schuurman, D. (2015). *Bridging the gap between Open and User Innovation? Exploring the value of Living Labs as a means to structure user contribution and manage distributed innovation.*

³⁶ Kviselius, N.Z., Ozan, H., Edenius, M., & Andersson, P. (2008). *The Evolution of Living Labs: Propositions for Improved Design and Further Research.*

Figure 6 Analytical framework of the living lab innovation levels (Kviselius, 2008)

Since 2015 the 3-layered model of Schuurman is widely adopted within the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) and has proven to be very helpful in the support of (emerging) living labs concerning the pathways to sustainability as a (harmonized) living lab. Furthermore, multiple Horizon projects (e.g., Rewaise³⁷, SCORE³⁸, Open Lab³⁹) are using this approach to support the set-up of sustainable living labs as well.

Therefore, **understanding the different levels of a living lab is crucial before starting the set-up** of such a constellation & project(s).

3.1.3 Key elements of a living lab

When it comes to describing the key elements of a living lab (within all three levels of a living lab) our research shows that, multiple authors use different descriptions to identify these elements.

Back in 2008, Mulder & all⁴⁰, were one of the first to describe **six views** upon a living lab: *User involvement, Service creation, Infrastructure, Governance, Innovation outcomes, and Methods & tools*.

Four years later (2012), Ståhlbröst & Holst⁴¹ identified **5 components & 5 key principles** of a living lab:

- 5 components of a living lab: *ICT & infrastructure, management, partners & users, research, approach*.
- 5 key principles: *value, influence, sustainability, openness, realism*.

Cremers⁴², in 2015 mentioned **5 features** of a living lab: *characteristics and roles of the participants, the working culture, the organization, educational activities, the physical and virtual environment*.

Two years later (2017), Steen & Van Bueren⁴³ used **4 dimensions** of defining characteristics: *Aims, Activities, Participants, Context*.

³⁷ <http://rewaise.eu/>

³⁸ <https://score-eu-project.eu/>

³⁹ <https://openlab-project.eu/>

⁴⁰ Mulder, Ingrid & Velthausz, Daan & Kriens, Martijn. (2008). *The Living Labs Harmonization Cube: Communicating Living Lab's Essentials*.

⁴¹ Stahlbröst, A., Holst, M. (2012) *SmartIES The living lab methodology handbook*.

⁴² Cremers, P. (2015): *Guidebook living Labs: tool for designing and evaluating living labs at the interface between school and workplace*.

⁴³ Steen, K., & van Bueren, E. (2017). *The Defining Characteristics of Urban Living Labs*.

Westerlund & all⁴⁴ provided us in 2018 with **9 constructs**, offering a multi-faceted perspective to understanding living labs: *objective, governance, stakeholders, openness, funding, value, communication, infra-structure, methods*.

In the same year (2018), Chroner & all⁴⁵ defined **6 main components** of a living lab: *an innovation to experiment with, citizens to engage, a mix of methods for engagement of different stakeholders and data collection, management structure for governance, infrastructure to support real-life experimentation, a mixture of partners with stable and dynamic relationships*.

Finally, Zipfel & all⁴⁶ described in 2022, **5 key components** of living labs: *user- centric, cocreation, real- life context, test innovation and open innovation*.

Next to these approaches from the academic world our research found also examples from 3 projects:

- the iScape⁴⁷ living lab implementation plans mentions **5 common elements** are mentioned: *active user-involvement, real-life setting, multi-stakeholder participation, multi-method approach, co-creation*.
- the Looper⁴⁸ guidelines for living labs mentions **6 main components**: *place, people, priorities, platform, process-setup, process-evaluation*.
- the UNALAB⁴⁹ living lab handbook mentions **7 key components**: *governance and management structure, financing and business model, urban context, nature-based solutions, partners & users, approach and methods, ICT infrastructure*.

Finally, we looked at the application guidelines⁵⁰ of the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) to add their **6 chapters** from a living lab: *organization, resources, openness, users & reality, value, business model and plans for the future*.

To map all different descriptions, we made a comparison between them and matched them against the standardized framework as proposed by Vervoort & all⁵¹, 2021 since that seemed to be the most comprehensive framework covering all these elements (see 2.3.2).

⁴⁴ Westerlund, M., Leminen, S. & Habib, C. (2018). Key Constructs and a Definition of Living Labs as Innovation Platforms.

⁴⁵ Chroner, D., Stahlbrost, A., Habibpour, A. (2018). Towards a unified definition of urban living labs.

⁴⁶ Zipfel N, Horreh B, Hulshof CTJ, et al. (2022) The relationship between the living lab approach and successful implementation of healthcare innovations: an integrative review.

⁴⁷ <https://www.iscapeproject.eu/>

⁴⁸ <https://looperproject.eu/>

⁴⁹ <https://unalab.eu/en/documents/urban-living-lab-handbook>

⁵⁰ <https://enoll.org/about-us/how-to-become-a-member/>

⁵¹ Vervoort, K. ; Trousse, B. ; Desole, M. ; Bamidis, P. ; Konstantinidis, E. ; Santonen, T. ; Petsani, D. ; Servais, D. ; De Boer, D. ; Spagnoli, F. ; Onur, O. & Bertolin, J. (2022) Harmonizing the evaluation of living labs: a standardized evaluation framework.

The table here below shows this mapping.

2021	2007	2012	2015	2017	2018	2018	2022	iScale	Looper	UNALAB	ENoLL
Vervoort & all Strategy	Mulder	Stahibrost & Holst	Creemers	Steen & Van Bueren Aims	Westerlund & all Objectives	Chroneer & all	Ziptel & all		Priorities		Organization
Governance	Governance	Management	Organization	Aims	Governance	Management structure			Process-set up	Governance & management structure	Business model & plans for the future
Business Model	Service creation				Funding				Priorities	Financing and business model	Business model & plans for the future
Culture & collaboration			Working culture	Participants	Communication	A mixture of partners with stable relationships				Partners & users	
Operations											
Human Resources			Characteristics & roles of the participants	Participants							Resources
Operations		Research approach	Organization	Activities		Innovation to experiment	Co-creation	Co-creation	Process-set up	Approach & methods	
Equipment & infrastructure	Infrastructure	ICT & infrastructure	Physical & virtual environment	Context	Infrastructure	Infrastructure to support real-life experimentation	Test innovation		Platform	ICT & infrastructure	Resources
Openness											
Innovation partnerships, projects & processes		Openness		Openness		Open innovation				Openness	
Innovation partnerships, projects & processes		Partners & users			Stakeholders			Multi-stakeholder participation	People	Partners & users	
Ownership of results											
User & reality											
User centrality	User involvement	Influence	Characteristics & roles of the participants	Participants	Stakeholders	Citizens to engage	User-centric	Active user-involvement	People	Partners & users	Users & reality
Lifecycle/ real-life		Realism	Physical & virtual environment	Context		Real-life experimentation	Real-life context	Real-life settings	Place	Urban context	Users & reality
Tools & methods	Methods & tools				Methods	Mix of engagement methods		Multi-method approach	Process-set up	Approach & methods	
Impact & value											
Co-created values	Innovation outcomes	Value	Educational activities		Value				Process-evaluation		Value
Impacts	Innovation outcomes								Process-evaluation		
Stability & harmonization											
Stability		Sustainability			Funding					Financing and business model	Business model & plans for the future
Harmonization & scale-up	Service creation					A mixture of partners with stable relationships					Business model & plans for the future

Figure 7 Comparison key elements from research and practice

Based on the outcomes of this comparison we propose to use all terms which were mentioned at least 6 times (out of 11) as key elements of a living lab. Obviously not ignoring the importance of those mentioned fewer times.

Therefore, **we define following 7 key elements of a living lab**. These 7 key elements of a living lab are crucial to be assessed and monitored during the onboarding, running and harmonization phases.

We rank them here below based on the amount of mentions in the table here above:

1. **User centrality** (11 out of 11)
2. **Equipment & infrastructure** (10 out of 11)
3. **Governance** (9 out of 11)
4. **Real-life context** (9 out of 11)
5. **Co-creation projects & processes** (8 out of 11)
6. **Tools & methods** (6 out of 11)
7. **Co-created values** (6 out of 11)

If one of these key elements is lacking within an organization, it could no longer be 'labelled' as a living lab.

3.1.4 Checklist Understanding the living lab concepts.

- What is a living lab?
- What are the three levels of a living lab?
- What are the key elements of a living lab?

3.2 Assess your living lab status.

3.2.1 Need of assessment

Alonso & all (2021)⁵² are clearly indicating that **checking compliance with living lab principles (see 3.1) in all the stages if the living lab processes is crucial to safeguard the sustainability of a living lab.**

⁵² Alonso Raposo, M., Mourzouchou, A., Garus, A., Brinkhoff-Button N., Kert K. and Ciuffo, B., (2021): JRC Future Mobility Solutions Living Lab (FMS-Lab): Conceptual framework, state of play and way forward.

This vision is supported by the view of Gago & Rubalcaba (2021)⁵³ describing **the need of a lifecycle approach to study living labs covering the 3 phases of onboarding, running and harmonization**, referred to by the authors as: inception (concept & organisation), activities (role of co-creation), public value and metrics (impact).

In addition to this the APRILab⁵⁴ guidelines mention any case study should **start with a critical analysis of the context**: Is it a living lab? If not, how might it become one?

Finally, ENOLL's Virtual Learning Lab⁵⁵, aimed at bringing together a community of participants and experts in exchanging knowledge on the key elements of living labs, is offering a modulated online course around following key elements:

- *LL basics, vision & openness*
- *stakeholder engagement*
- *implementation & strategic plans*
- *governance model*
- *business model*
- *co-creation & experimentation*
- *promotion and communication*

Linking these insights with the inputs from the first step of this guideline framework (see 3.1), **an assessment by organizations wanting to become a living lab is needed prior to starting the set-up of the living lab** to benchmark their status on all crucial aspects of the living lab concepts and to identify their strengths and weaknesses in relation to them.

Therefore, within Task 2.3 'Establishment of evaluation process and tools', a self-assessment tool covering all these aspects will be developed and made available. Further development on this will be reported within D4.6 'Guidelines framework (final version)'.

3.2.2 Checklist Assess your living lab status.

- To which degree is my organization a living lab according to the harmonized definition of a living lab?
- To which degree is my organization aligned with the key elements of a living lab?
- Is my organization willing/able to take the necessary steps to set up a living lab based on the 3-layered model?

3.3 Set up the living lab.

3.3.1 Components of setting up a living lab

Once an organization has identified their status and made the decision to move forward with the set-up of a 3 layered living lab enough attention, time and resources are needed to organize the living lab in such ways it has the highest chance of sustainability in the long-term.

Multiple authors are providing us with insights into the crucial steps to be taken to this regard. The most mentioned aspects are about the strategy and the governance of the living lab.

The most complete approach is offered by Kalinauskaite & all (2021)⁵⁶, identifying 4 stages of setting up a living lab:

1. stakeholder mapping
2. scope definition
3. strategic impact mapping

⁵³ Gago, David & Rubalcaba, Luis. (2021). *Inception, activities, and performance of Spanish living labs: a comparative approach*.

⁵⁴ <https://studylab.net/doc/18183370/the-urban-living-lab-guidelines-for-aprilab>

⁵⁵ <https://openlivinglabdays.com/virtual-learning-lab/>

⁵⁶ Kalinauskaite, I.; Brankaert, R.; Lu, Y.; Bekker, T.; Brombacher, A.; Vos, S. (2021) *Facing Societal Challenges in Living Labs: Towards a Conceptual Framework to Facilitate Transdisciplinary Collaborations*.

4. roadmap definition

Figure 8 Conceptual framework depicting important stages to facilitate collaboration initiation phase.

In addition to this, Sarrabi & all (2020) indicates there is a need for a flexible governance approach, while Kviselius & all (2008) and den Ouden & all (2016) are both mentioning the need of a governance approach which is **Urging partners to actively govern the innovation process** through regulating its support processes. This will provide commitment from partners well as transparency to the Living Lab which will increase long-term support for the Living Lab. The living lab as an orchestrator safeguards joint interests and maximizes social value, while ensuring that all involved parties contribute and get their fair share of the benefits.

To ensure that a common vision is indeed shared by all, **stakeholder alignment on various levels is crucial**. Scholars outline the importance of integration of **common concepts and knowledge**, creation of **shared strategy and values** as well as a balance of mutual and individual gains (Kalinauskaite & all, 2021).

This approach is also adopted by the JRC mobility solution labs (Alonso Raposo & all, 2021) since they mention one should start any living lab work by planning and **defining aims, target users and stakeholders**, and **ways to effectively engage users and all stakeholders throughout the living lab projects**, while setting up a **living lab steering committee** to support the strategic and operational activities of the living lab with a **clear and shared strategic direction and vision**, developing communication strategy and tools.

Likewise, Cremers (2015) indicates **the design of a living lab is shaped by the starting points**. There is always some motive or urgency for starting a living lab, and its aims and ambition can be deduced from it. The aims and ambition are also determined by the context and prerequisites (i.e., the participating partners, the position of the living lab, and the available resources, such as people and funding).

The **team design of a qualified staff** covering all necessary roles within a living lab team plays an equally important role.

Looking at all these different inputs, the crucial elements of setting-up a living lab are:

- Strategy (vision, mission, objectives & roadmap)
- Governance (stakeholders & decision-making processes)
- Business model (value propositions & financial engineering)
- Operations (human resources & equipment/infrastructure)
- Innovation projects (living lab methodologies, user engagement & communication)

Detailed guidelines & recommendations for each of these elements will be developed within D4.6 'Guidelines framework (final version)'.

A great tool for keeping track of all these elements is the living lab mapping canvas developed by ENoLL. It provides an overview of all the crucial elements of a living lab within all three levels of a living lab (macro-meso-micro) and can be used not only during the onboarding phase, but also during the running and harmonization phases of a living lab. The tool is being updated on a regular base to safeguard alignment with the most recent academic and practical insights.

More information about this tool can be requested via info@enoll.org.

Appendix 4 is showing the living lab mapping canvas of ENoLL.

3.3.2 Checklist Set up the living lab.

From this step onwards we will link the questions in this checklist with the numbers of the related KPIs from the KPI table (Table 4), we put the KPI number between brackets here below.

- Did we map all the relevant stakeholders to be involved? (2)
- Do we have a shared vision and mission? (1)
- Is a living lab steering committee in place? (3, 6, 8)
- Who's paying/contributing in what to safeguard the financial balance of our living lab? (7)
- Do we have a value proposition for clients? (4, 5)
- Is our living lab team fully equipped? (11, 12, 13)
- Are the necessary equipment & infrastructures in place? (17, 18, 19)
- Do we have our first innovation project(s) defined? (14, 21, 22)
- What's our user engagement strategy? (26, 27, 28, 32, 34)
- How does our internal and external communication strategy look like? (8, 9, 10)

3.4 Execute living lab projects & activities.

The next step of a living lab is to gain experiences and to 'fail forward' by executing living lab projects and activities. These **projects and activities are characterised by the user centrality within an integrative process** (lifecycle approach), **using a multi-method approach for ensuring participants are engaged within their real-life contexts.**

As Cremers (2015) mentions, the outcomes are brought about by processes of interactive knowledge production. Examples of such processes are acquiring and applying knowledge, research, finding new combinations, co-creating knowledge and products, building social capital, reflection, self-directed learning, etc.

In this deliverable we scope the important aspects of running a living lab project and/or activity. More in-depth recommendations will be provided within D4.6 'Guidelines framework (final version)'.

3.4.1 User centrality

According to the European Commission⁵⁷ user-centricity means '*putting users' needs at the centre when determining which public services should be provided and how they should be delivered.*

⁵⁷ <https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/collection/nifo-national-interoperability-framework-observatory/glossary/term/user-centricity>

Therefore, as far as possible, user needs and requirements should guide the design and development of public services, in accordance with the following expectations: i A multi-channel service delivery approach; ii A single point of contact should be made available to users; iii Users' feedback should be systematically collected, assessed, and used to design new public services and to further improve existing ones.'

Although the definition above is focusing specifically on the development of public services it fits the intentions of user-centricity within living labs. The term 'public services' in the definition can be simply replaced by the identified objectives of the living lab within the previous step of this guideline framework.

The aim of user engagement is to give users the opportunity to decide on the solution that will affect their life later-on. Doing so increases the level of acceptance and success of the developed solution.

The international association for public participation (IAP2)⁵⁸ developed a spectrum of public participation to assist with the selection of the level of participation that defines the public's role in any public participation process. This model is widely adopted within living labs and helps them to actively involve stakeholders and users throughout innovation projects.

	INFORM	CONSULT	INVOLVE	COLLABORATE	EMPOWER
PUBLIC PARTICIPATION GOAL	To provide the public with balanced and objective information to assist them in understanding the problem, alternatives, opportunities and/or solutions.	To obtain public feedback on analysis, alternatives and/or decisions.	To work directly with the public throughout the process to ensure that public concerns and aspirations are consistently understood and considered.	To partner with the public in each aspect of the decision including the development of alternatives and the identification of the preferred solution.	To place final decision making in the hands of the public.
PROMISE TO THE PUBLIC	We will keep you informed.	We will keep you informed, listen to and acknowledge concerns and aspirations, and provide feedback on how public input influenced the decision.	We will work with you to ensure that your concerns and aspirations are directly reflected in the alternatives developed and provide feedback on how public input influenced the decision.	We will look to you for advice and innovation in formulating solutions and incorporate your advice and recommendations into the decisions to the maximum extent possible.	We will implement what you decide.

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Figure 9 Spectrum public participation (IAP2)

3.4.2 Lifecycle approach/ Integrative process

Using **the lifecycle approach and/or the integrative process** within your living lab projects **ensures** you of **involving all relevant stakeholders throughout the full development process of the innovation.**

The lifecycle approach means users are involved in 4 stages of the innovation:

- Ideation
- Co-creation
- Experimentation

⁵⁸ <https://www.iap2.org/page/pillars>

- Validation

The living lab integrative process as introduced by Mastelic⁵⁹ in 2019 is a further enrichment to this approach, describing these stages in a more elaborative way. Involving users from the problem phase to the deployment phase. She described 6 steps:

- Selecting a practice
- Integrating stakeholders
- Uncovering the barriers
- Co-designing the plan.
- Piloting an intervention
- Evaluating performance

However, to cover the macro-level of a living lab focusing on the long-term beyond an individual living lab project, two more steps were added.

As shown in Figure 8 here below, taken from the SCORE living lab methodology, users are actively involved in the definition, the ideation, the prototyping, and testing phases of an innovation, while the innovation is implemented and ideally scaled-up outside the initial scope of the project.

Living Lab Integrative Process - Design thinking

*Adapted from Mastelic, 2019

Figure 10 Living Lab integrative process (adapted from Mastelic, 2019)

Both models are also related to the Technology Readiness Level Framework for the living labs as proposed within D2.5 'Standard version 4'.

The Technology Readiness Level (TRL) Framework for the living labs is suggested to be a suitable approach to define and describe living lab innovation process maturity stage. However, in living lab innovation process, the “Technology” term must be interpreted as any product/service/system/method/ solutions or similar tangible realization of the idea that is being

⁵⁹ https://www.hevs.ch/media/document/3/phd_joelle_mastelic_sept_2019_vf.pdf?1567114480

developing, not only as “technology” per se. Therefore, term “solution” is preferred in living lab context instead of technology.

However, this TRL framework looks at the innovation process from a technology perspective while the Living Lab Integrative Process and the lifecycle approach are approaching it more from the user involvement perspective.

Table 5 here below shows the correlation between the three different approaches.

Table 5 Comparison lifecycle approach, living lab integrative process and TRL framework living labs.

Lifecycle approach	Ideation		Co-creation		Experimentation	Validation		
	Living Lab Integrative process	Select a practice	Integrate stakeholders	Uncover barriers	Co-design plan	Pilot an intervention	Evaluate performance	Demonstrate the system
Technology Readiness Level Framework	TRL1	TRL2	TRL3	TRL4	TRL5	TRL6	TRL7/TRL8	TRL9

To develop solutions which are the closest as possible to the daily activities of the involved end-users it's crucial to test & experiment the solutions in their real-life contexts.

In a living lab, innovations, technologies, products, solutions & services are transferred to these daily life contexts of users instead of bringing the users to a 'closed' testing environment to interact with the innovations.

Therefore, it's essential to make sure tests & experiments are taking place within real-life environments of users as much as possible. Logically, the real-life context is mainly taking place within the experimentation phase (lifecycle approach) / pilot and evaluation phases (living lab integrative process).

Some examples to clarify this a bit more:

- When developing a new type of home for elderly people offering them to possibility to remain longer at home before moving to a nursery home, the technologies are implemented in the actual living spaces of the participating elderly persons instead of moving the persons to a demo house.
- When developing a solution to reduce floods within neighborhoods, the innovations are implemented within that actual neighborhood instead of within a safe and closed test site.

3.4.3 Tools & methods

Within a living lab, a wide variety of participatory tools and methods is being used to engage and interact with participants. The research tools & methods are always chosen based on the expected outcomes of the living lab activity and not the other way around (adapting the way of running the activity to the research method chosen). This offers a high flexibility to adjust the next planned activities within the innovation project based on the feedback and outcomes of the previous activity.

Some excellent examples of developed toolkits for participatory tools & methods are:

- UNALAB tools for co-creation⁶⁰
- SISCODE toolbox for co-creation journeys⁶¹

⁶⁰ <https://unalab.enoll.org/>

⁶¹ <https://siscodeproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/toolkit-27092019-1.pdf>

- The Design Kit from [ideo.org](https://www.designkit.org/methods.html)⁶²

The list of good examples on participatory tools & methods is presented in the corresponding LL Harmonization wiki and is constantly updated⁶³.

3.4.4 Checklist Execute living lab projects & activities.

We link the questions in this checklist with the numbers of the related KPIs from the KPI table (Table 4), we put the KPI number between brackets here below.

- Are the living lab projects designed to cover the lifecycle approach and/or integrative process of living labs? (29)
- To which degree are users involved in the development of the innovation? (27)
- Are solutions tested and experimented within real-life contexts of the users? (30, 31)
- Are participatory tools & methods relevant for all planned activities? (32, 33)

3.5 Monitor your progress & impact.

Monitoring your living lab on all three levels is essential in reaching a higher level of maturity and to learn from your experiences. The monitoring should not only include project & activity related items, but also governance and strategy related items. Doing so will offer the possibility to adapt/develop a service portfolio in the long-term to increase the sustainability of the living lab (see 3.8) and prepare the living lab for a more harmonized approach (see 3.9).

Colobrans (2019)⁶⁴ endorses this approach by stating: *'To be able to evaluate the degree to which the initial objectives have been achieved it is necessary to create a set of indicators. The state of these indicators needs to be recorded at the start of the research and again once the project has concluded and considering the results. Depending on the duration of the project it is also advisable to gather partial data in case it is necessary to take executive decisions about the way the project is proceeding. Comparing the initial and final state of the indicators enables the effect of the changes carried out during the project to be ascertained. These **indicators are established at two levels: for the Living Lab as a whole and for each of its pilot projects taken individually.***

In addition to this Overdiek & Genova (2021)⁶⁵ emphasize the fact that the focus of the assessments needs to be determined from the beginning, next to the definition of the roles of who's the evaluation tools are provided for. Furthermore, the authors stress that there's a need to **develop more playful and creative ways to evaluate living lab activities and their impacts** with the goal of inspiring, learning, and increasing the completion of the designed monitoring frameworks.

This approach is further supported by Michael Quinn Patton, founder of the Utilization-Focused-Evaluation (UFE)⁶⁶ method, based on the principle that evaluation should be judged on its usefulness to its intended users. Therefore evaluations/monitoring activities should be planned and designed in ways that enhance the likely utilization of both the findings and of the process itself to inform decisions and improve performances.

Finally, Mastelic & all (2015)⁶⁷ highlight that monitoring frameworks should consider 3 dimensions of the living lab:

- time: *a progressive approach in the evaluation of living labs*
- space: *how scalable and replicable to other spaces and geographic reaches*
- dynamic nature: *changes from one type of innovation to another*

⁶² <https://www.designkit.org/methods.html>

⁶³ <https://wiki.livinglab-harmonization.com/xwiki/bin/view/Data%20Collection%20Approaches/>

⁶⁴ Colobrans, J. (2019) *Mindb4ACT Living Lab Guide*

⁶⁵ Overdiek, A. & Genova, M. (2021), *White Paper, Evaluating living labs? Methods and tools.*

⁶⁶ <https://www.utilization-focusedevaluation.org/>

⁶⁷ Mastelic, J., Sahakian, M., Bonazzi, R. (2015), "How to keep a living lab alive?"

Looking out the outcomes of the literature review and desktop research on evaluation/monitoring of living labs, following aspects of a living lab should be monitored:

- *The defined SMART goals & objectives (governance)*
- *The efficiency of decision-making processes (governance)*
- *The evolution of the service portfolio (business model)*
- *The frequency of internal communication & results sharing (culture & collaboration)*
- *The evolution of (internal/external) staff (human resources)*
- *The efficiency of living lab project & activities (operations)*
- *The outcomes of living lab projects & activities (operations)*
- *The quality & presence of equipment & infrastructures (equipment & infrastructures)*
- *The coverage of ethical necessities (innovation partnerships, projects & processes)*
- *The coverage & presence of rules, regulations & agreements concerning feedback protection and IP (ownership of results)*
- *The intensity of user involvement (user centricity)*
- *The coverage of the integrative processes (lifecycle/real-life)*
- *The concreteness of the real-life contexts (lifecycle/real-life)*
- *The efficiency of used methods & tools (tools & methods)*
- *The user & stakeholder satisfaction rate concerning their involvement (co-created values)*
- *The improvement of operational excellence (impacts)*
- *Societal, environmental, economic, regulatory, and academic impacts depending on the objectives of the living lab (impacts)*
- *The financial balance (funding vs. other revenue streams) of the living lab (stability)*
- *The products/solutions/services ready for scale-up (harmonization & scale-up)*
- *The collaboration with other (networks of) living labs (harmonization & scale-up)*

Next to this, also the frequency of monitoring/evaluation should be defined and agreed upon.

The chapters, criteria and KPIs (see 2.3.4.6) from the standardized evaluation framework (see 2.3.4.5) will be used to further develop a self-assessment tool for living labs within Task 2.3 "Establishment of evaluation process & tools".

3.5.1 Checklist Monitor your progress & impact.

We link the questions in this checklist with the numbers of the related KPIs from the KPI table (Table 4), we put the KPI number between brackets here below.

- Are the necessary aspects which require monitoring identified? (15)
- Is the monitoring framework designed in such a way that ensures the utilization of it? (8, 9)
- What is the frequency of monitoring the aspects? (16)
- How and for whom will the results be reported? (8,9,34)

3.6 Learn from others.

Feurstein & all (2008)⁶⁸ highlight the fact that beyond the implementation of individual Living Labs, **a networked approach to the concept offers several significant benefits**. den Ouden & all (2016)⁶⁹ underline this as well, not only focusing on **an internal open atmosphere within the ecosystem** that addresses the collaboration between industry, government, citizens, and academia, existing out of ambitious people who understand the challenges and are willing to contribute with the prospect of being able to benefit from the innovation. Learning from other living labs and outcomes of other living lab projects will fast-track the growth to maturity of the living lab. Therefore, we strongly advise to search for living labs with similar objectives and reach out to them to organize bilateral learning exchanges on organizational and operational level.

⁶⁸ Feurstein, K & Hesmer, A & Hribernik, K. & T., Klaus-Dieter & Schumacher, J. (2008). *Living Labs: A New Development Strategy*.

⁶⁹ den Ouden, P. H., Valkenburg, A. C., & Blok, S. (2016). *Exploring the future of living labs: research report*

3.6.1 Checklist Learn from others.

We link the questions in this checklist with the numbers of the related KPIs from the KPI table (Table 4), we put the KPI number between brackets here below.

- Are similar living labs identified? (10)
- Have bilateral learning exchanges been set-up? (10)

3.7 Join thematic/geographical working groups & networks.

Schuurman & all (2013)⁷⁰ emphasise that **networking between living labs** is not only desirable for encouraging sustainability and fostering further retention processes, but would also **facilitate the exploration and exploitation processes, such as assessments of technologies with larger user groups**.

Vontas & Protogeros (2009)⁷¹ add to this vision by mentioning networking between living labs will **increase the reputation** of each individual living lab.

Alonso & all (2021)⁷² highlight that **collaborations represent opportunities for scaling up** the activities of their Future Mobility Solution-Lab, which pave the way to a higher impact of the living lab work, allowing to assess replicability of living lab activities and transferability of results from living lab research.

Several living lab networks are active. Most of them offer thematic and/or regional networking opportunities. Also, there are networking activities that are created because of projects. We'd like to highlight that the list living lab networks mentioned here below is not exhaustive.

3.7.1 European Network of Living Labs

The eldest and largest network is the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL)⁷³, founded in 2006 under the Finnish presidency of the council of the European Union.

According to their website, they offer a growing path for their members, focusing on the certification of living labs⁷⁴ (+500 labelled living labs), building capacities for them and empowering deep knowledge exchange and project building within their Action Oriented Task Forces. These task forces offer thematic focus around emerging topics like health and well-being, energy and environment, mobility, social impact of AI, social innovation, living labs as regulatory tools, etc.

Since 2010, ENoLL organizes yearly the biggest living lab gathering conference, Open Living Lab Days⁷⁵.

Anno 2023 ENoLL has 158 active members, spread over 36 countries and 5 continents.

3.7.2 Le Forum des Living Labs en Santé et en autonomie (Forum LLSA)

Since 2011, the Forum LLSA⁷⁶ has been supporting the actors of innovation in Health and Autonomy: professionals, institutions, academics, and associations. Through a patient-centered approach, the association federates the Living Labs ecosystem by encouraging the emergence of new projects through the establishment of working groups on key topics in health and innovation and by working on new concepts and methodologies, with the aim of advancing the health of tomorrow.

⁷⁰ Schuurman, Dimitri & Marez, Lieven & Ballon, Pieter. (2013). *Open Innovation Processes in Living Lab Innovation Systems: Insights from the LeYLab*.

⁷¹ Vontas, A. & Protogeros, N. (2009). *Evaluating living labs core competences and assets*.

⁷² Alonso Raposo, M., Mourtzouchou, A., Garus, A., Brinkhoff-Button N., Kert K. and Ciuffo, B., (2021): *JRC Future Mobility Solutions Living Lab (FMS-Lab): Conceptual framework, state of play and way forward*.

⁷³ <https://enoll.org/>

⁷⁴ <https://enoll.org/membership-wave/>

⁷⁵ <https://openlivinglabdays.com/past-editions/>

⁷⁶ <https://www.forumllsa.org/>

Their aim is to recognize territorial living lab initiatives in health, promoting inter-regional links, accelerating the sharing of experiences and good practices and the promotion of French know-how at European and international level.

3.7.3 Australian Living Labs Innovation Network (ALLIN)

The Australian Living Lab Innovation Network⁷⁷ is being developed since 2016, running a series of symposia and contributing to the Manifesto of open innovation. They have signed a memorandum of understanding with ENoLL (see 3.7.1) and are being involved in the establishment of living labs in Australia with ENoLL accreditation.

Their aim is to promote living labs in Australia, fostering collaboration opportunities with existing living labs in Europe and the Asia Pacific. Next to this they develop the practitioner base to support living lab development and promote inter-disciplinary approaches to innovation across universities, business, industry, and government.

3.7.4 Living Lab networks on the Northern America continent

Our research identified two more active living lab networks on the Northern America continent.

The Lake Superior Living Labs Network (LSELLN)⁷⁸ support and strengthens existing sustainability-related teaching, research, and action initiatives on local, regional and watershed scales. Furthermore, they enhance governance structures to ensure equitable and meaningful long-term partnerships.

The Canadian Agroecosystem Living Labs Network⁷⁹, founded by Agriculture and Agri-food Canada (AAFC) promotes and collaborates on the agroecosystem living labs approach.

3.7.5 Project living lab networks.

We also identified 3 networks which are aimed to be created within European projects:

- The DESIRA Living Labs⁸⁰ are 20 networks of stakeholders established across Europe and selected to represent a variety of agricultural, rural and forestry domains.
- The European Union Mission “A Soil Deal for Europe”⁸¹ aims to establish 100 Living Labs and Lighthouses to lead the transition towards healthy soils by 2030.
- ALL-Ready⁸² aims to prepare a framework for a future European network of Living Labs (LL) and Research Infrastructures (RI) that will enable the transition towards agroecology throughout Europe.

3.7.6 VITALISE Harmonization Body group.

This group was created as part of the VITALISE H2020 project and will develop a sustainability plan to continue its activities after the end of the project. Anyone can be enrolled in the VITALISE Harmonization Body group⁸³ and follow the Harmonization activities that are taking place.

3.7.7 Checklist Join thematic/geographical working groups & networks.

We link the questions in this checklist with the numbers of the related KPIs from the KPI table (Table 4), we put the KPI number between brackets here below.

- Is your living lab collaborating within living lab networks? (47)
- Which thematic focus networks are you looking for? (47)

⁷⁷ <https://www.australianlivinglabs.com.au/about/>

⁷⁸ <https://livinglabs.lakeheadu.ca/living-lab-approach/lake-superior-living-labs-network/>

⁷⁹ <https://agriculture.canada.ca/en/science/living-laboratories-initiative/living-laboratories-initiative-international-engagement-and-partnerships>

⁸⁰ <https://desira2020.eu/living-labs/>

⁸¹ <https://prepsol.eu/living-labs-and-lighthouses>

⁸² <https://www.all-ready-project.eu/index.html>

⁸³ <https://vitalise-project.eu/harmonisation-body/>

3.8 Achieve sustainability (financial, value propositions, skills & knowledge)

Next to the **interaction and collaboration with other living labs** tackled in the previous step of this guideline framework, proven to be a crucial aspect in the long-term success (sustainability) of living labs, for a Living Lab to create sustainability, **its partners must feel that it gives them the best return on their innovation investments.** (Kviselius & all, 2008)⁸⁴.

This is also acknowledged by Santonen & all (2020)⁸⁵ mentioning improved collaborations with a reliable partner network & customers are equally important.

Furthermore, the same authors indicate stabilized living labs appears to have **more mature technical infrastructure and facilities**, which is considered as an important resource and an enabler. These living labs are highlighting more the R&D service activities, which is also reflected into **multiple living lab value propositions.**

Bodi, de Los Rios White & Enriquez (2020)⁸⁶ specify **understanding the strengths, values and weaknesses of each Living Lab** is critical for its survival and sustainability. Creating a viable business model that offers value to all different types of new and/or involved stakeholders is key to the sustainability of a Living Lab via reaching a (high level) of financial maturity based on a balanced & diversified set of funding & revenue streams by the development of multiple living lab value propositions.

Finally, Vontas & Protogeros (2009)⁸⁷ clarify what the added values of a solid living lab business plan are:

- *new and improved services which can be replicated and scaled-up.*
- *new methods & tools which can be replicated and scaled-up.*
- *new and/or improved infrastructures which can be replicated and scaled-up.*
- *increased potential and skill improvement of employees*

Therefore, it's our strong recommendation to map the living lab value propositions, revenue streams and cost structures via the Living Lab Business Model Canvas (LIAISON), developed by Bertolin⁸⁸. This open-source tool, a combination of the business model canvas from Osterwalder⁸⁹, the running lean canvas from Ash Maurya⁹⁰ and the social lean canvas from Yeoman & Moskovitz⁹¹, offers all elements for a living lab to create a solid business plan.

⁸⁴ Kviselius, N.Z., Ozan, H., Edenius, M., & Andersson, P. (2008). *The Evolution of Living Labs: Propositions for Improved Design and Further Research.*

⁸⁵ Santonen, T.; Julin, M.; Salmi, A. & Leskinen, J. (2020) *Understanding the underlying factors of living lab business model.*

⁸⁶ Bodi, Z., de Los Rios White, M., Enriquez-Florez, L. (2020): *Rewaise Living Lab Methodology and online handbook.*

⁸⁷ Vontas, A. & Protogeros, N. (2009). *Evaluating living labs core competences and assets.*

⁸⁸ https://energylivinglab.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/6.1_ImplementScale-up_Liailon-BMC.pdf

⁸⁹ <https://www.strategyzer.com/canvas/business-model-canvas>

⁹⁰ <https://leanstack.com/lean-canvas>

⁹¹ <https://www.theimpactinitiative.org.nz/toolkit-for-se/social-lean-canvas>

Figure 11 Living Lab Business Model Canvas (LIAISON) by Juan Bertolin

This Living Lab Business Model Canvas is also included in the LL Harmonization wiki⁹² and will be updated in the next Standard version. The LL Harmonization wiki LIAISON presents an initial proposal for the specific fields for Health & Wellbeing LLs, and it can be further updated and adapted to the specific fields and needs of each LL.

3.8.1 Checklist Achieve sustainability.

We link the questions in this checklist with the numbers of the related KPIs from the KPI table (Table 4), we put the KPI number between brackets here below.

- Are the internal collaborations between partners of the living lab future proof? (42, 45)
- Is the living lab performing a regular SWOT exercise concerning the organizational (macro) and operational (meso-micro) levels? (43)
- Which (new) living lab propositions have been developed? (44, 46,48,49)
- How does your financial balance look like (funding vs. other revenue streams)? (43)

3.9 Using/developing harmonized living lab infrastructures, technical standards, processes, services, tools & methods

A sustainable living lab is encouraged to 'harmonize' its activities to further increase the viability of the living lab in the long-term.

Santonen & all (2020)⁹³ developed a transnational living lab collaboration maturity model (TLLCMM) highlighting **access to (other living lab) services, knowledge & technologies** while learning from them & **further develop (own) living lab services** will help to expand the visibility, marketing and networking of the living lab and increase the chances of gaining more international funding.

⁹² <https://wiki.livinglab-harmonization.com/xwiki/bin/view/Living%20Lab%20Business%20Model/>

⁹³ Santonen, T.; Kjellson, F.; Andersson, K. & Hirvikoski, T. (2020) Developing maturity model for transnational living lab collaboration.

Figure 12 Transnational Living Lab Maturity Model (TLLCMM) Santonen & all 2020

Already back in 2007, Mulder & all⁹⁴ attempted to **harmonize living lab practices**, derived from the assumption that focusing on those elements that Living Labs want to exchange is an appropriate basis for harmonization of methods and tools.

However, harmonization of living labs goes beyond using/developing harmonized tools & methods.

Although, Feurstein & all (2008)⁹⁵ confirmed the input from Mulder & all stating that disseminating this information into different Living Labs, training the stakeholders in the region to understand and use new methods and tools will allow later a comparison of the results throughout the created (living lab) network, they also stress that **standardization and certification play a big role**. Effort needs to be made to link together **the infrastructures** found in the individual living labs without needing to be concerned about **interoperability issues**.

Again Santonen & all (2022)⁹⁶ added to this by pointing out that **a harmonized research protocol** speeds up & improves the research quality within living labs.

Next to this Petsani & all (2022)⁹⁷ emphasize that **a shared and harmonized vocabulary** such as the proposed taxonomy **makes living labs more accessible** for newcomers as well as stimulates cross-organizational and research collaboration due to a unified language. This language should deal with all living lab definitions and key elements (see 3.1), living lab projects, processes & activities (see 3.4), tools & methods (see 3.4), and skills (see 3.3).

The Vitalise Wiki⁹⁸, developed within WP2 'Harmonization activities', not only offers such a harmonized vocabulary within the living lab lexicon (see 2.3.4.8), but also contains harmonized definitions of living lab business models, research and innovation processes, R&D services, research infrastructures, data collection approaches, and devices and technologies. The VITALISE Wiki is the first systematic attempt to present a harmonized framework for Health and Wellbeing LLs. The Living Labs can use it to achieve Harmonization in the following ways:

⁹⁴ Mulder, I., Fahy, C., Hribernik, K., Velthausz, D., Feurstein, K., Garcia, M., Schaffers, H., Mirijamdotter, A., & Stahlbrost, A. (2007). *Towards harmonized methods and tools for Living Labs*

⁹⁵ Feurstein, K & Hesmer, A & Hribernik, K. & T., Klaus-Dieter & Schumacher, J. (2008). *Living Labs: A New Development Strategy*.

⁹⁶ Santonen T, Petsani D, Julin M, Garschall M, Kropf J, Van der Auwera V, Bernaerts S, Losada R, Almeida R, Garatea J, Muñoz I, Nagy E, Kehayia E, de Guise E, Nadeau S, Azevedo N, Segkoulis S, Lazarou I, Petronikolou V, Bamidis P, Konstantinidis E. (2022) *Cocreating a Harmonized Living Lab for Big Data–Driven Hybrid Persona Development: Protocol for Cocreating, Testing, and Seeking Consensus*

⁹⁷ Petsani, D., Santonen, T., Konstantinidis, E., Enriquez, Petronikolou, V., Maga, C., Makroglou, S., Bamidis, P. (2022) *Towards a Taxonomy for Health Living Lab Data Collection Devices*.

⁹⁸ <https://wiki.livinglab-harmonization.com/bin/view/Main/>

1. Refer to the harmonized vocabulary within the living lab lexicon section, to refer to certain terminology and their adaptation in the Living Lab framework.
2. Get information about the LL R&D services and map their own provisions. In that way each LL can create a list of the R&D services that they provide and inform the external researchers and LL practitioners.
3. Each R&D Service provides a detailed description so that everyone provides this service in a harmonized way.
4. An extensive taxonomy for devices and technologies used for data collection in the Health & Wellbeing domain. The LLs can map their devices in these taxonomies so that they provide a harmonized reference to external researchers.

3.9.1 Checklist Using/developing harmonized living lab infrastructures, technical standards, processes, services, tools & methods.

We link the questions in this checklist with the numbers of the related KPIs from the KPI table (Table 4), we put the KPI number between brackets here below.

- Which elements of the living lab are (ready to be) harmonized? (46,48,49)
- Which harmonized elements are being developed by the living lab? (46,48,49)

3.10 Collaborate in (cross-border/cross-sectoral) projects/networks based on harmonized infrastructures, technical standards, processes, services, tools & methods.

The last step after the adoption of harmonized infrastructures, technical standards, processes, services, tools & methods is to work together based on these harmonized infrastructures, technical standards, processes, services, tools & methods with other living labs in projects & programs.

Feurstein & all (2008)⁹⁹ underline that by offering a **broader base for co-creation and market analysis activities**, customers are guaranteed better, more differentiated, and more comparable feedback. Products and services can for example be co-created either specifically for one regional market, analyzed across several different cultural backgrounds or targeted at a wider market.

den Ouden & all (2016)¹⁰⁰ support that view by mentioning these **projects should be part of a program that strives to cross boundaries**.

Finally, ENOLL's experiences on cross-border and cross-sectoral collaborations crossing these boundaries shows that **the future of living labs is moving towards more and more transnational living lab collaborations models**, as mentioned by Santonen & all in their TLLCMM (see 3.9).

Projects within the portfolio of ENOLL¹⁰¹ like Vitalise, Prepsoil, ALL-Ready, DT4 Regions, SCORE, and Transformer confirm that direction, since they are all focusing on cross-border or cross-sectoral platforms for collaboration within different fields of society like health, agriculture, climate change and social innovation.

3.10.1 Checklist Collaboration in a harmonized way

We link the questions in this checklist with the numbers of the related KPIs from the KPI table (Table 4), we put the KPI number between brackets here below.

- In how many (cross-border/cross-sectoral) harmonized projects is the living lab involved? (50)

⁹⁹ Feurstein, K & Hesmer, A & Hribernik, K. & T., Klaus-Dieter & Schumacher, J. (2008). *Living Labs: A New Development Strategy*

¹⁰⁰ den Ouden, P. H., Valkenburg, A. C., & Blok, S. (2016). *Exploring the future of living labs: research report*.

¹⁰¹ <https://enoll.org/projects/>

4 Next steps

This document will be updated in M36 within deliverable D4.6 "Living Lab guidelines (final version)". The next steps that will be taken in the upcoming 12 months within this guideline framework will also support the further development of deliverables:

- D2.7 "Standard version 6"
- D4.2 "Online educational material (final version)"
- D4.4 "Printed educational material (final version)"

To start with, the desktop research (see 2.2) around living lab guidelines and harmonization of living labs will be continued to further enrich the guideline framework with new insights. Simultaneously, within Task 2.3 "Establishment of evaluation process & tools" we will focus on the following steps to strengthen the evaluation framework and support the development of a self-assessment tool for living labs:

- continue the literature review with the reading of the orange-coloured papers as mentioned within 2.3.4.1 Literature review of this deliverable to iterate the KPI table (see 2.3.4.6)
- validate the current criteria descriptions (see 2.3.4.5) and KPI table (see 2.3.4.6)
- define scoring tables for each criterion to benchmark the maturity of living labs regarding that specific criterion.
- determine the necessary formulas to calculate that maturity correctly.
- design the evaluation methods to collect the evaluation from living labs.
- support the development of a self-assessment tool, based on these previous steps.

Each of these steps will be piloted internally in collaboration with the Vitalise pilot group (existing out of members of ENoLL and Forum LLSA) and validated internally by this pilot group and the Vitalise harmonization board and externally by the ENoLL labelling task force and a group of academic living lab experts.

Regarding each step of the guideline framework (see 3 Step by step) we aim to provide supporting educational material and/or detailed guidelines (in line with D4.2 "Online educational material (final version)", and D4.4 "Printed educational material (final version)").

More in detail, following steps are planned for:

- 3.1 Understand the living lab concepts:
 - internal & external validation of the harmonized definition of a living lab, the description of the 3-layered model and the 7 key elements of a living lab.
 - continue the literature review and desktop research on key elements of living labs to add new insights for the comparison table (see Table 2).
- 3.2 Assess your living lab status:
 - support the development of a self-assessment tool.
- 3.3 Set up the living lab:
 - continue the literature review and desktop research on the crucial elements of setting up a living lab to add new insights.
- 3.4 Execute living lab projects & activities:
 - add more good examples to the list of participatory tools & methods.
- 3.5 Monitor your progress & impact:
 - update living lab aspects to be monitored based on new insights.
- 3.6 Learn from others:
 - add recommendations to interact with other living labs.
- 3.7 Join thematic/geographical working groups & networks:
 - update the list of living lab networks.
 - add information on how to join these networks.
- 3.8 Achieve sustainability:
 - add information on tools to measure sustainability.
 - support the development of a self-assessment tool.

- 3.9 Using/developing harmonized infrastructures, processes, standards, methods & tools:
 - add in-depth definitions of the different harmonized living lab elements.
 - add recommendations on how to harmonize these elements.
- 3.10 Collaborate in (cross-border/cross-sectoral) projects/networks based on harmonized infrastructures, processes, standards, methods & tools:
 - add good examples of collaboration in a harmonized way.
 - add information on how to discover opportunities for harmonized collaboration.

5 Conclusions

This document presents information about the development within the first 24 months of Vitalise of a first version of a living lab guideline framework, based on literature review and desktop research, supported by the work done within Task 2.3 "Establishment evaluation process & tools".

The final outcomes of this guideline framework will be reported within deliverable D4.6 " Living Lab guidelines (final version)".

From the work that has been done so far, the authors conclude that this first version of a guideline framework provides a solid structure to support living labs in reaching a higher level of harmonization, which will help them to become more sustainable in the long-term.

However, as explained in the previous chapter 4 (Next steps) this first version is a work in progress and more work is needed to harmonize the support for living labs in growing towards sustainability.

The design of this guideline framework is done in a utilization focused approach, involving key internal (Vitalise pilot group and harmonization board) and external (ENoLL labelling task force and group of academic living lab experts) stakeholders in the whole process.

Following this approach is safeguarding that the outcomes of this first version and the final version of the guideline framework (D4.6) are relevant to and adopted by the living lab community.

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Appendices

Appendix 1

The desktop research around guidelines for living labs resulted in the index as shown here below:

Title	Citation	Author(s)	Year of publication	Guidelines	How to set up a living lab	Harmonization	Academic paper	Project outcomes	Online sources
Agrilink Assessment tool: conditions for a living lab	https://edepot.wur.nl/572086	Potters			1			1	
Aprilab: The Urban living lab: guidelines for APRILab	Wallin, S. (2014) APRILab: Guidelines to Define and Establish an Urban Living Lab	Sirkku Wallin	2014					1	
Are living labs effective? Exploring the evidence	Krassimira Paskaleva, Ian Cooper, Are living labs effective? Exploring the evidence	Krassimira & Cooper	2020		1		1		
Barriers to the adoption of urban living labs for NBS implementation - a systemic perspective	Sarabi, S.; Han, Q.; L. Romme, A.G.; de Vries, B.; Valkenburg, R.; den Ouden	Sarabi & all	2021		1		1		
Co-Val: Inception, activities and performance of spanish living labs: a comparative approach	Co-Val	Gago & Rubalca	2019					1	
Cocreating a harmonized living lab for Big Data-driven hybrid persona development: protocol for cocreating, testing, and seeking	Santonen T, Petsani D, Julin M, Garschall M, Kropf J, Van der Auwera V, B	Santonen & all	2022			1	1		
Creatifi: Implementation living lab methodology	Creatifi: https://cordis.europa.eu/docs/projects/cnect/5/632905/080/deli	Aversano, Baccarne & Schuurman	2016			1		1	
Developing maturity model for transnational living lab collaboration	Santonen, T.; Kjellson, F.; Andersson, K. & Hirvikoski, T. (2020) Developing	Santonen & all	2020			1	1		
EIT Urban Mobility tools and learning practices	https://livinglabs.eitum.eu/tools/		2020	1	1				1
ENoLL Application guidelines wave 2023	https://enoll.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/application-guidelines-wave-2023-13122022.pdf		2023	1	1				1
ENOLL Virtual learning lab	https://openlivinglabdays.com/virtual-learning-lab/		2023	1	1				1
EU Macs: guidelines for living labs in climate services	https://eu-macs.eu/outputs/livinglabs/	Ines Vaittinen	2021	1					1
Evaluating living labs core competences and assets	Vontas, A. & Protogeros, Nicolaos. (2009). Evaluating living labs core com	Vontas & Protogeros	2009			1	1		
Evaluating living labs? Methods and tools	Anja Overdiek & Mari Genova, November 2021, White Paper, The Hague U	Anja Overdiek	2021			1	1		
Exploring the future of living labs	den Ouden, P. H., Valkenburg, A. C., & Blok, S. (2016). Exploring the future	Den Ouden & all	2016		1		1		
Facing Societal Challenges in Living Labs- Towards a Conceptual Framework to Facilitate Transdisciplinary Collaboration	Kalinauskaitė, I.; Brankaert, R.; Lu, Y.; Bekker, T.; Brombacher, A.; Vos, S. F	Kalinauskaitė & all	2021		1		1		
Hanze University: Guidebook living labs - Tool for designing and evaluating living labs at the interface between school and work	https://fontys.nl/Over-Fontys/Nieuws-tonen-op/3_Guidebook-Living-Labs	Cremeres P.	2015		1			1	
Harmonizing the evaluation of living labs	Vervoort, K., Servais, D., & Trousse, B. & all (2022). Harmonizing the evalu	Vervoort & all	2022			1	1		
How to keep a living lab alive?	Joëlle Mastelic Marlyne Sahakian Riccardo Bonazzi, (2015), "How to keep	Mastelic & all	2015		1		1		
IScape: implementation plan for the IScape living labs	www.iscapeproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/06/ISCAPE_D2.2_Living-Lab-implementation-plans_-v05_FINAL.pdf		2017	1	1			1	
JRC Future mobility solutions living lab - conceptual framework, state of play and way forward	Alonso Raposo, M., Mourtzouchou, A., Garus, A., Brinkhoff-Button N., Kert	Alonso Raposo & all	2021		1		1		
Key Constructs and a Definition of Living Labs as Innovation Platforms	Westerlund, Miika & Leminen, Seppo & Habib, Christ. (2018). Key Construct	Westerlund & all	2018		1				
LightSense Living Lab handbook	https://www.light-sense.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/Deliverable-D7.1-Living-Lab-handbook.pdf				1			1	
Living Labs - a new development strategy	Feurstein, K & Hesmer, A & Hribernik, Karl & Thoben, Klaus-Dieter & Schur	Feurstein & all	2008			1	1		
Living Labs - From niche to mainstream innovation management	Greve, K.; Vita, R.D.; Leminen, S.; Westerlund, M. Living Labs: From Niche	Greve & all	2021		1		1		
Living Labs as open innovation networks - Networks, roles and innovation outcomes	Leminen, Seppo. (2015). Living Labs as Open Innovation Networks - Netw	Leminen S.	2015		1		1		
Living Labs in the context of the UN SFGs: state of the art	Leal Filho, W., Ozuyar, P.G., Dinis, M.A.P. et al. Living Labs in the context o	Filho & all	2022		1		1		
Living Labs Past Achievements, Current Developments, and Future Trajectories	Schuurman, D.; Leminen, S. Living Labs Past Achievements, Current Develo	Schuurman & Leminen	2021		1	1	1		
LOOPER: Guidelines for the living labs	LOOPER: http://looperproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/08/LOOPER	Ravetz, Evans & Astbury	2018	1	1			1	
MINDbACT Living Lab Guide		Jordi Colobrans	2019					1	
Open innovation business models- the example of living labs	Ingrid Fasshauer. Open Innovation Business Models - the example of living	Fasshauer I.	2020		1		1		
Open innovation processes in living lab innovation systems - Insights from the LeyLab	Schuurman, Dimitri & Marez, Lieven & Ballon, Pieter. (2013). Open Innova	Schuurman & all	2013			1	1		
Open learn create online course on living labs	https://www.open.edu/openlearncreate/mod/oucontent/view.php?id=173529		2020		1				1
Protocol for a systematic review of living labs in healthcare	Archibald M, Wiebe S, Rieger K, et al. Protocol for a systematic review of	Archibald & all	2021		1		1		
REWAISE Living Lab methodology and online handbook	http://rewaise.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/05/REWAISE-LL-online_hand	Bodi, de Los Rios White & Enriquez Florez	2020	1	1			1	
SCORE: The coastal cities living lab framework & methodology	SCORE	de Los Rios White & Vervoort	2022					1	
SmartIES Living Labs methodology handbook	SmartIES	Stahlbrost & Holst	2012		1			1	
The defining characteristics of Urban living labs	Steen, K., & van Bueren, E. 2017. The Defining Characteristics of Urban Liv	Steen & Van Bueren	2017		1		1		
The Evolution of Living Labs – Propositions for Improved Design and Further Research	Kviselius, Niklas & Ozan, Håkan & Edenius, Mats & Andersson, Per. (2023)	Kviselius & all	2009		1		1		
The Hitchhiker's guide to successful living lab operations	Alan Wang, Feng Yi Change, Siavash Yousefi, Beatrice Li, Brad Campbell, a	Wang & all	2022		1		1		
The HSB living lab harmonization cube	Sasic Kalagasidis, A., Hagy, S., Marx, C. (2017). The HSB Living Lab harmon	Kalagasidis & all	2017			1	1		
The relationship between the living lab approach and successful implementation of healthcare innovations: an integrative review	Zipfel N, Horreh B, Hulshof CTJ, et al. The relationship between the living	Zipfel & all	2022		1		1		
Towards a taxonomy for health living lab data collection devices	Petsani, D.; Santonen, T.; Konstantinidis, E.; Enriquez, L.; Petronikolou,	Petsani & all	2022			1	1		
Towards a unified definition of urban living labs	Chroneer, D., Stahlbrost, A., Habibipour, A.(2018). Towards a unified definit	Chroneer & all	2018		1	1	1		
Towards harmonized methods and tools for living labs	Mulder, I., Fahy, C., Hribernik, K., Velthaus, D., Feurstein, K., Garcia, M., S	Mulder & all	2008			1	1		
U4IoT Living Lab methodology handbook	U4IoT	Evans & all	2017		1			1	
UNALAB Living Lab Handbook for Urban living labs developing nature-based solutions	https://unalab.eu/	Habibipour & all	2021		1			1	
Understanding the underlying factors of living lab business model	Santonen, T.; Julin, M.; Salmi, A. & Leskinen, J. (2020) Understanding the	Santonen & all	2020		1		1		

Appendix 2

KPI Sentences for a living lab evaluation framework

Hello,

One of the cornerstones of ENoLL (<https://enoll.org/>) is the **high-quality labelling and certification process** which is in place to evaluate living lab (members).

Since living labs evolve over time it's crucial to constantly improve this **evaluation structure** on a continuous base to make sure it keeps fitting the high-quality standards required and **to support living labs in assessing themselves to grow and remain sustainable.**

Monitoring living lab activities, projects, and organizations (micro-, meso- and macro-level) **in a standardized way isn't easy** and the creation of a self-assessment tool for living labs will be win-win situation for everyone.

Within the Vitalise project (<https://vitalise-project.eu/>), we are striving for the creation of an improved evaluation structure and process for living labs.

Last year **a renewed evaluation framework was co-designed with living lab experts and a pilot group of living labbers** from the ENoLL and Forum LLSA network.

This resulted in an academic paper which you can find here below:
https://www.academia.edu/81060356/Harmonizing_the_evaluation_of_living_labs_a_standardized_evaluation_framework

Today we ask your cooperation to **continue the development of this framework by refining the descriptions of each criterion.**

Completing this survey will take approximately 19 minutes. We hope to receive your feedback Friday March 24 at 23.59h CEST at the very latest.

If you have any questions or remarks. Don't hesitate to contact us via koen.vervoort@enoll.org

Thank you so much for using your precious time to help us,

Koen, Evdokimos, David and the whole Vitalise, ENoLL and LLSA Forum team.

* Required

GDPR

1

By completing this form you agree to your details being held electronically by the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL). ENoLL will process your personal data on the legal basis of Art. 6, case b) of GDPR. Your data will be processed in compliance with Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council, of 27 April 2016, on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (GDPR) and Law 2018/40581 of 30 of July 2018 on protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data.

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Do you agree with the statement above? *

Yes

No

The evaluation framework

The framework exists out of **6 chapters and 15 criteria**.

We sketch the complete framework here below before diving deeper into it chapter by chapter and asking your feedback for all criteria one by one.

Strategy

- Governance
- Business Model
- Culture

Operations

- Human resources
- Operations
- Equipment & infrastructure

Openness

- Innovation processes & partnerships
- Ownership of results

Users & reality

- User centricity
- Lifecycle & real life
- Tools & methods

Impact & Value

- Co-created values
- Impacts

Stability & harmonization

- Stability
- Harmonization & scale-up

We would kindly ask you to **review the sentences we prepared for each criterion**.

To help you we added screenshots of the earlier collected input for every criterion above the proposed sentences.

To make everything 100% clear: we are creating sentences based on the orange post-its (sub criteria). The yellow post-its are inputs for measuring the KPIs (Key Performance Indicators) later.

These sub criteria were ranked by the experts and the pilot group during multiple on-line workshops

Strategy

This chapter focuses on the **macro-level** of a living lab, considering the *multi stakeholder participation* and the *orchestration* role of the living lab, looking at their *collaboration* strategies, while investigating the *business model* of the living lab as well. Within this chapter the LL is evaluated against 3 criteria:

i) **Governance**, in terms of a well-defined and shared vision & mission for the living lab, based on real identified needs of the quadruple helix which is reviewed on a regular and flexible basis (macro), involvement of all actors of the quadruple helix (on a strategic level) within a well described and flexible partner network (macro), team design (clearly defined roles and responsibilities within the living lab management & coordination team) (macro) and finally a clear description about the expected impacts of the LL strategy and the LL projects (macro)

ii) **Business Model**, in terms of financial engineering (sustainable finances) (macro), and a well-defined and described service portfolio (for various types of innovation and collaboration processes)(macro)

iii) **Culture**, in terms of proof of connections/interest to connect with external (regional/national/ international) innovation ecosystems (macro), smart and adaptive co-operation/collaboration within the living lab design to build trust (macro-meso) and quality of the internal communication processes, channels & tools within the living lab to build trust (macro-meso-micro)

Next we will **show you the input** that we collected earlier around this chapter and **ask you to vote for your preference** on the proposed sentences. Feel free to add an own suggestion that would fit even better according to you.

Governance

2

Which sentence describes best the criterion here above? *

- The Living Lab governance is SMART if it includes all the major actors of quadruple helix (academia, industry, public authorities, and citizens) along with a systematic participative approach, a shared vision and mission which can impact the Living Lab strategy and the projects for better outcomes and a clear Team Management (which means a clear definition of each actor roles).
- A Living Lab governance model involves all actors of the quadruple helix in a systematic participative approach, based on a shared vision & mission, to impact the Living Lab strategy & projects, supported by a clear Team Management plan.
- Other

Business Model

3

Which sentence describes best the criterion here above? *

- A solid living lab business model enables the living lab to strengthen its status & service portfolio via active stakeholder partnerships & financial engineering
- The business model of a living lab clearly describes their service portfolio and stakeholders partnerships to increase their status, supported by a solid financial engineering
- Other

Culture

Which sentence describes best the criterion here above? *

- The culture of a living lab enhances internal and external collaboration, based on communication & collaboration strategies
- The culture of a living lab empowers internal collaboration & communication strategies and strenghtens external collaborations, within an open & solid project culture
- Other

Operations

This chapter is covering **all levels** of a living lab, looking at the way the living lab manages its operations, considering the necessary equipment & infrastructure and human resources of the living lab. Within this chapter of the evaluation 3 criteria are defined:

i) **Operations**, in term of proof of experience in running living lab projects and activities, including described examples (meso-micro), installed monitoring processes for operational aspects of the living lab (research, innovation funnel, project management) (macro-meso), installed monitoring processes for measuring the impact of LL activities, LL projects and the LL strategy overall (macro-meso-micro), implemented partner agreements within the living lab (macro-meso) as well as branding and positioning of the living lab (macro-meso)

ii) **Human resources**, in terms of availability & assignment of qualified staff in different roles & responsibilities (labor division) (macro) and role fluidity (clear role distribution adapted in the basis of needs) (macro-meso)

iii) **Equipment & infrastructure**, in terms of access to necessary living lab equipment & infrastructures (e.g., software, hardware, spaces) (macro-meso-micro) and availability of necessary living lab equipment & infrastructures (e.g., software, hardware, spaces) indicated in time (macro-meso-micro)

Next we will **show you the input** that we collected earlier around this chapter and **ask you to vote for your preference** on the proposed sentences. Feel free to add an own suggestion that would fit even better according to you.

Human resources

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5

Which sentence describes best the criterion here above? *

- The living lab has clearly defined roles in place and people assigned to them in a flexible & effective way based on competences required & skills available
- The human resources of the living lab are designed and implemented in a SMART way to ensure the necessary flexibility within the living lab team
- Other

Operations

6

Which sentence describes best the criterion here above? *

- The quantity and quality of living lab projects, activities, branding, and agreements are followed up by a monitoring process
- The living lab shows experience in executing monitored projects and activities, within the scope of their branding (positioning) and based on clear partner agreements
- Other

Equipment & infrastructure

7

Which sentence describes best the criterion here above? *

- The living lab has access to the available equipment & infrastructure they need in an easy, stable & structured way.
- Equipment & infrastructure needed to run the living lab are available in an accessible & structured way.
- Other

Openness

This chapter investigates the openness of the living lab from a **macro-, meso- and micro- level perspective**, by focusing on the *processes*, the *partnerships*, the *feedback & IP protection*. Within this chapter of the evaluation 2 criteria are defined:

i) Innovation processes & partnerships, in terms of presence of agreements covering legal aspects of the living lab (insurances, mutual responsibilities) (macro-meso), presence of the necessary transparent data agreements between the living lab and its partners, stakeholders & users (macro-meso), level of transparency of the living lab (macro) and openness towards new partners and investors (macro)

ii) Ownership of results, in terms of feedback protection (meso-micro), shared ownership vs. Formal ownership (macro-meso) as well as quality of the IP processes in place describing the living lab activities supporting capability and openness (meso-micro)

Next we will **show you the input** that we collected earlier around this chapter and **ask you to vote for your preference** on the proposed sentences. Feel free to add an own suggestion that would fit even better according to you.

Innovation processes & partnerships

8

Which sentence describes best the criterion, here above? *

- The living lab has a transparent way of dealing with open innovation processes & partnerships (including the necessary legal agreements)
- The living lab approaches their (new) partnerships, but also innovation projects & processes in a open & transparent way, resulting in clear legal internal and external agreements
- Other

Ownership of results

Which sentence describes best the criterion here above? *

- Ownership of the results is protected and allows users to be involved in the results of the living lab
- The living lab has monitored & transparent processes & agreements to protect stakeholders' feedback and property rights (IPR)
- Other

Users & reality

This chapter investigates the *ways of collaboration with users* and the levels of engagement & participation, by focusing on the implementation of an *iterative living lab process in real-life settings* and investigating the quality of used *tools & methods*. Therefore, it relates to the **macro-, meso- and micro-level** of a living lab. Within this chapter of the evaluation 3 criteria are defined:

i) Quality of the iterative living lab processes in real-life settings, in terms of adoption of an iterative living lab process based on the lifecycle approach and/or the living lab integrative process (meso) and involvement of users in real life settings (e.g., at home, work, in the public space) (meso-micro)

ii) User-centricity of the user & stakeholder engagement approach, in terms of description and intensity of the user participation & user impact on the innovation process (macro-meso), representativity of the user panel in relation to the amount of actively involved users in the living lab activities (meso-micro), level of permanence of the user panel (beyond project scale) (macro) and amount of actively involved users in the living lab activities (micro)

iii) Quality of the participatory tools & methods, in terms of engagement strategies (e.g., via partners) to match evolving needs of users (macro-meso), range of used tools & methods (meso-micro), quality and innovativeness of tools & methods to involve (groups of) people in the different steps of the iterative living lab process (meso-micro) as well as quality of the external communication processes, channels & tools to attract new partners, stakeholders, and users (macro-meso).

Next we will **show you the input** that we collected earlier around this chapter and **ask you to vote for your preference** on the proposed sentences. Feel free to add an own suggestion that would fit even better according to you.

User centricity

Which sentence describes best the criterion here above? *

- A user-centric living lab has an active (long-term) user panel that represents its ecosystem, influencing the outcomes of projects & activities.
- Within the living lab, users are regularly represented within a strong panel
- Other

D4.5 Living Lab guidelines first version.

Lifecycle & real-life

11

Which sentence describes best the criterion here above? *

- A user-centric living lab involves users, in their specific real-life context, throughout the complete lifecycle and/or living lab integrative process
- The living lab actively interacts with users in every phase of the innovation process/project within realistic real-life settings of them
- Other

Tools & methods

12

Which sentence describes best the criterion here above? *

- A user-centric living lab engages & interacts with its users in a structured way, using a wide range of quality tools & methods
- The living lab has strong engagement strategies, supported by clear communication processes, using a wide range of co-creation tools & methods
- Other

Impact & value

This chapter assesses the *co-created values* (e.g., knowledge sharing, capacity building, network building) by whom but even more importantly for whom. Furthermore, it investigates different *impact aspects* of the living lab (e.g., societal, economic, environmental...). Therefore, this chapter is related to **all levels** of a living lab. Within this chapter of the evaluation 2 criteria are defined:

i) **Co-created values**, in terms of user and stakeholder satisfaction (e.g., influence on the process & products, shared values, purpose) (macro-meso-micro), degree of knowledge exchange among living lab actors (macro-meso-micro), academic validation for researchers (e.g., publications, real case studies, cross-sectoral & cross-border "authorship", conference (participation/invitation...)) (macro-meso), knowledge sharing among network actors (e.g., presence of a community platform/knowledge platform, shareable results, tech transfer) (macro-meso), capacity building for/by network actors (e.g., developed training materials for/by stakeholders, experts created by the living lab, study credits, academic courses) (macro-meso), TRL level of developed technologies (e.g., adoptability in operational environments, replicability in other settings) (meso), value chain entities covering (macro-meso) and degree of value capture strategies (macro-meso- micro)

ii) **Impact of the living lab**, in terms of internal impact corresponding to what degree did the different levels of the living lab learned from each other (macro-meso-micro), societal impact (e.g., behavioral change, inclusion, diversity, digital gap) (macro-meso), economic impact (e.g., patents, market disruption, speed of market penetration, decrease of cost, increase of profit, improved value proposition of the living lab) (macro-meso), environmental impact (e.g., reduction of pollution, decrease of weather events, increase of air quality) (macro-meso) and regulatory impact (e.g., public policies, standardization of regulatory requirements, marketing authorization) (macro-meso).

Next we will **show you the input** that we collected earlier around this chapter and **ask you to vote for your preference** on the proposed sentences. Feel free to add an own suggestion that would fit even better according to you.

Co-created values

13

Which sentence describes best the criterion here above? *

- The living lab focuses on knowledge sharing & capacity building, based on value capturing strategies, to cover its value chain and to satisfy ensure his users & stakeholders satisfaction
- The living lab builds capacities of their users & stakeholders, based on their satisfaction, and co-creates shared (academic) knowledge, validating these outcomes in a structured way throughout their value chain.
- Other

Impacts

14

Which sentence describes best the criterion here above? *

- A living lab creates impacts (also internal) beyond the project scale: societal, environmental, economic, regulatory and/or others.
- Based on their strategies the living lab creates (long-term) impacts within one or more of following aspects of their ecosystem: societal, environmental, economical, regulatory
- Other

Stability & harmonisation

The final chapter focuses on the (financial) *stability* of the living lab from a **macro-level** perspective, considering different needed aspects like business model, service offerings (e.g., processes, procedures, policies, methodologies, tools & methods...) and strategy plans. Aligned with this, this chapter looks at the level of harmonisation of these strategical and operational building blocks beyond the living lab (in relationship to other LLs, RIs and open innovation orchestrators) since this will increase the sustainability of the living lab. Consequently, it mainly deals with the macro level. Within this chapter of the evaluation 2 criteria are defined:

- i) **Stability of the living lab**, in terms of degree of achieved funding (macro), degree of new partnerships (macro), degree of network collaboration (local to international) (macro-meso), SWOT analysis (e.g., risk assessment, self-reflection, unique selling points) (macro) as well as business plan for the future (e.g., financial balance projects vs. Service offering) (macro).
- ii) **Harmonisation & scaling-up**, in terms of adoption of standardized living lab procedures (ethics, IP approach, quadruple helix involvement) (macro-meso), adoption of standardized project management processes (living lab integrative) (macro-meso), adoption of standardize tools, methods & technologies (e.g., access to other living labs services, knowledge and technologies while learning from them to further develop own living lab services) (macro), replicability of the service offering/value proposition (scaling-up) (macro), quality of cross-sectoral and geographical collaboration (macro), quality of knowledge sharing in comparison with other LLs & RIs (macro) and quality of capacity building in comparison with other LLs & RIs (macro)

Next we will **show you the input** that we collected earlier around this chapter and **ask you to vote for your preference** on the proposed sentences. Feel free to add an own suggestion that would fit even better according to you.

Stability

15

Which sentence describes best the criterion here above? *

- A sustainable living lab focuses on improving collaborations with internal and external partners, based on a solid business plan including an analysis of its own strengths & weaknesses.
- A stable living lab is monitoring his strengths & weaknesses, identifying opportunities & threats to increase collaborations with internal and external partners in order to guarantee a balanced business plan
- Other

Harmonisation & scale-up

16

Which sentence describes best the criterion here above? *

- A sustainable living lab offers knowledge & services in a standardized way (within their sector(s)) that are replicable in other sectors and regions/countries/ continents
- The Living Lab has the capacity to replicate and conduct similar projects in other environments through a willingness to standardize its methods & tools and share its results
- Other

Pilot group Vitalise

Thank you so much for your input.

Your feedback will help us to continue with our next steps:

- Creation of a scoring table for each criterion
- Creation of a survey to measure maturity of living labs
- Creation of a self-assessment tool for living labs

In the upcoming months (April-June 2023) we will co-create these steps further together with the pilot group in our Vitalise project.

If you'd feel like to be (re-)invited for these online workshops, please make sure to complete your personal information on the next page.

17

Do you want to be (re-)invited for these online workshops (April-June 2023)? *

Yes

No

Personal information for participation in the pilot group

18

What's your full name? *

19

What's your email address? *

20

What's the name of your organization you're working for? *

21

Which networks is your organisation affiliated to? *

- ENoLL (European Network of Living Labs)
- Forum LLSA (Forum des Living Labs en Santé et Autonomie)
- None of the above
- Other

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Appendix 3

Strategy

- **Governance**

- Involvement Q4/5 actors:
 - *The different types of stakeholders involved (iScape/SISCODE/Score/Rewise/Water Europe/ProVaHealth/Co-act/Forum LLSA/Living Lab Markers)*
 - *Level of involvement in the governance of stakeholders (iScape/ SISCODE/ Open lab/Forum LLSA)*
 - *Sufficient motivation of actors to collaborate (Van Geenhuizen)*
- Shared vision & Mission
 - *A co-created common vision/mission aligning expectations/motives & values within the stakeholder network (Kalinauskaite/Leminen/Veeckman/Water Europe/B-water Smart/Co-act/various external)*
 - *Strategic areas/thematic focus & priorities (Kalinauskaite/Veeckman/Open Lab/SCORE)*
- Participate approach/open governance
 - *Clearly defined roles and open interrelations of actors (McPhee/Galway/Ståhlbrost/iScape/Vitalise/SCIROCCO/Living Lab Markers)*
 - *Agreed processes of decision-making (Galway/Rewise/Forum LLSA/SCANBALT)*
 - *Involvement of users in governance (Living Lab Markers/forum LLSA)*
 - *Inclusion of different levels (strategic & operational) into the governance structure (Mulder/Santonen)*
 - *Flexibility of the governance structure to adjust/adapt (Nystrom)*
- Expected impacts, strategy & projects
 - *Determination of the initial objectives and SMART goals (Kalinauskaite/Aquilué/Leminen/SCORE/Water Europe/SCIROCCO)*
 - *A strategic plan/impact map/roadmap (Kalinauskaite/iScape/SCORE)*
 - *Strategy to support both market & supply driven demands (Santonen)*
- Partner agreements
 - *Existence of partner agreements (Haug/Galway/iScape/open Lab)*
 - *Number of agreements (Open Lab/Vitalise/B-water smart/Water Europe/SCANBALT)*
- Team design
 - *Clear responsibilities of the governance actors (Westerlund/SCORE/Forum LLSA/Water Europe/B-water smart)*
 - *% personnel/actor (Vitalise)*
 - *Number of partners involved (Vitalise)*

- **Business model**

- Service portfolio
 - *A value proposition is in place (Vitalise/iScape/Forum LLSA)*
 - *Customers are defined (Mastelic)*
 - *Services covering the lifecycle approach (e.g., idea generation, collaborative innovation, validation & experimentation, market implementation support) are in place (Mulder/Water Europe/SCANBALT)*
 - *Having unique infrastructure (Santonen)*
 - *Role as an ecosystem and project manager (Santonen)*
 - *Number of services/products/solutions offered (Open Lab/Vitalise/ Forum LLSA)*
- Stakeholder/contributor's partnerships
 - *Presence of institutional agreements/arrangement for co-innovation (Gago & Rubalca/Santonen/Vitalise/water Europe/SCORE)*
 - *Key partners as a resource (Santonen)*
 - *% formal vs. informal partnerships (SCORE/Vitalise/Water Europe)*
- Status of the organization
 - *% turnover from own service portfolio (Vitalise/Forum LLSA)*

- % private vs. public funding and/or infrastructure
(Mastelic/Santonen/SCORE/Vitalise/SCIROCCO/Forum LLSA/Water Europe)
- Financial engineering
 - Resources provided/stakeholder (SCORE/Rewaise)
 - Who's paying/contributing with what (personnel, budget, in-kind)
(Rewaise/Vitalise/SCORE)
 - Total amount of funding (SCORE/open lab/Vitalise)
- **Culture & collaboration**
 - Internal communication strategy
 - Ways & frequency of communication & results sharing
(iScape/SCORE/Open Lab/ Living Lab Markers/ Forum LLSA/ Water Europe/Co-act/ SCANBALT/Super MoRRI)
 - Internal collaboration strategy
 - Actor relation management process/strategy in place (Westerlund/iScape/Forum LLSA/Super MoRRI/Water Europe)
 - Actor expectation management process/strategy in place
(Habibipour/iScape/Forum LLSA/Super MoRRI/Water Europe)
 - Type & amount of activities/year (Open Lab/ B-water smart/SCANBALT/Co-act)
 - User community building (Osorio)
 - External collaboration strategy
 - Customer relation management process/strategy in place
(Westerlund/iScape/Forum LLSA/Super MoRRI/Water Europe)
 - Client contracts in place (SCANBALT)
 - Pan European relevance (Mulder)
 - Number of (long-term) collaborations with external innovation ecosystems (Open Lab/Vitalise/Co-act/iScape)
 - % of regional/national/international collaboration (Santonen/Forum LLSA/ SCANBALT)
 - Innovation culture
 - Transparent project selection (Van Geenhuizen)
 - Use of well-defined guidelines/standards for testing (SCANBALT)
 - Number of agreements covering the legal aspects of the living lab (e.g., insurances responsibilities/liabilities to staff/partners/participants, infrastructures, etc.)
(Open Lab/iScape/Water Europe)
- **Operations**
 - Human resources
 - Availability & Assignment
 - Qualified personnel (Mulder/SCORE/Vitalise/Open Lab/Rewaise/Forum LLSA/SCANBALT/Co-act/Various)
 - FTE of dedicated staff (Haug/SCORE/Open Lab/Super MoRRI)
 - Clear roles & responsibilities
(iScape/SCORE/open Lab/ Vitalise/Rewaise/Forum LLSA)
 - Skills of staff (Vitalise/open Lab/Rewaise)
 - deal with the unpredictability (Van Geenhuizen/Forum LLSA)
 - conflict handling (Van Geenhuizen/ Gago & Rubalca/various)
 - Boundary crossing thinking cooperation
(Van Geenhuizen/Gago & Rubalcaba/Vitalise/various)
 - Availability external experts (Vitalise/Water Europe)
 - Role fluidity
 - Interdisciplinary know-how (building) (SCANBALT/Water Europe/Forum LLSA)
 - Role distribution & flexibility (various)
 - Operations
 - Experience projects & activities
 - Maturity of organized projects/activities (iScape/open Lab)
 - Number of LL projects/activities (ENoLL labelling)
 - Project management methods in place (Forum LLSA/Vitalise/SCANBALT)
 - Monitoring processes

- *Existence of an evaluation/monitoring plan (Mulder/Van Geenhuizen/iScape/SCORE/Open Lab/Vitalise/Forum LLSA/ Water Europe/SCIROCCO/B-Water Smart/Co-act/Various)*
- *Frequency of monitoring (SISCODE/Vitalise)*
- *Evaluation/monitoring topics mentioned:*
- *Effectiveness of strategic decisions (Guzman/Leroux/Open Lab/Vitalise/Forum LLSA/Super MoRRI)*
- *Financial management (Forum LLSA/Super MoRRI)*
- *Impact KPI's (Open Lab/Forum LLSA/SCIROCCO/various)*
 - *sustainability (B-water smart)*
 - *policy impact (B-water smart)*
 - *transformation/improvement LL infrastructures (Mulder)*
- **Branding & positioning**
 - *operations & communication aligned with expectations users (Schuurman/iScape)*
 - *geographical positioning of the LL (Santonen)*
 - *level of attractiveness towards external investors (SCORE)*
- **Equipment & infrastructure**
 - **Availability**
 - *presence of facilities to collaborate on open innovation (Osorio/Westerlund/Veeckman/iScape/SCORE/Forum LLSA/Water Europe)*
 - *presence of networks to collaborate with (Westerlund)*
 - *availability of hardware (Westerlund/Veeckman/iScape/SCORE/Vitalise/Rewaise/Water Europe/SCIROCCO)*
 - *availability of software (Westerlund/Veeckman/iScape/SCORE/Vitalise/Water Europe/SCIROCCO/Co-act)*
 - *availability of sensors (Westerlund)*
 - **Access**
 - *% time of accessibility to the E&I for the LL (Open Lab/SCANBALT)*
 - *collaboration process present to operate E&I (Water Europe)*
- **Openness**
 - **Innovation partnerships, projects & processes**
 - **Transparency level**
 - *Transparent project roles, selection & execution (including accessible and understandable information) (Van Geenhuizen/Open Lab/SCANBALT/Super MoRRI/B-water smart/Co-act/various)*
 - *Balanced & harmonized participation, influence & responsibilities among partners (Ståhlbröst)*
 - *An ethical approach (e.g., regulatory requirements, data protection needed etc.) (Callari/Vitalise/Forum LLSA/ Super MoRRI/Co-act)*
 - **Openness partnerships**
 - *A reflective and iterative approach to transdisciplinary collaboration (Veeckman/Kalinauskaite/iScape/SISCODE/SCORE/Water Europe)*
 - *A mixed and large set of stakeholders involved to complement the value chain (Veeckman)*
 - *Lack of openness blocks the build-up of a good ecosystem (Veeckman)*
 - *Openness to new funding sources (SCORE)*
 - *Willingness to adapt the scope based on available funding (SCORE)*
 - **Ownership of results**
 - **Data agreements**
 - *open pseudonymized data for partners/stakeholders (Leminen/Open Lab/super MoRRI)*
 - *data management plan & agreements between partners (Open Lab/Water Europe/SCANBALT/Super MoRRI/Co-act)*
 - **Types of ownership**
 - *Data ownership of users (Habibipour/Co-act)*

- *Strategy & processes in place for ownership of the rights & profits (including data) of collaborative outcomes (Callari/iScape/SCORE/Water Europe/Super MoRRI/various)*
- IP Processes
 - *Rules & regulations regarding the use, sharing & licensing of IP (prior to the project) (Westerlund/Mulder/Veeckman/iScape/Forum LLSA/ Water Europe/SCANBALT/Super MoRRI)*
- Feedback protection
 - *User agreements in place (data, IPR, rights, liabilities) (Pitkänen/ Habibipour/ Vitalise/ iScape/Forum LLSA/Super MoRRI/various)*
- **Users & reality**
 - User centricity
 - *Representativity*
 - *(Demographic) Profiles & diversity of the end users (SISCODE/SCORE/Vitalise/LL Markers/Water Europe)*
 - Permanence user panel
 - *Level of permanence of the user panel (time) beyond living lab projects (Open Lab/Vitalise/Co-act/Forum LLSA)*
 - Intensity
 - *Power of users to define their role in the innovation process (Logghe & Schuurman)*
 - *Degree of influence users exert on the innovation & development processes (Ståhlbröst/Logghe & Schuurman/SCORE/Open Lab/Vitalise/SCIROCCO/Co-act)*
 - *Number of users involved in (all) the living lab activities (Open Lab/SCORE/Vitalise)*
 - *The role of users according to the possible levels of involvement (SISCODE/SCORE/Vitalise/Open Lab/Forum LLSA/SCANBALT/SCIROCCO/LL Markers)*
 - Lifecycle & real-life
 - *Lifecycle/ integrative process*
 - *Number of users involved in the different phase of the innovation cycle (Osorio/Aquilué/Open Lab/SCORE/Vitalise/iScape/SISCODE/LL Markers/Forum LLSA/SCANBALT/Super MoRRI/Co-act)*
 - *Quality of the integrative process (SCORE/Open Lab/Forum LLSA/Co-act)*
 - Real-life settings
 - *% time users participate in real-life settings (Van Geenhuizen/iScape/SCORE/Open Lab/LL Markers/Forum LLSA/SCANBALT)*
 - *Concreteness of real-life settings enabling participants to go beyond just a realistic scenario Van Geenhuizen/iScape/SCORE/Open Lab/LL Markers/Forum LLSA/SCANBALT)*
 - *Different dimensions of context (physical, temporal, task, social, technical & transitions (Coorevits & Jacobs, Forum LLSA)*
 - Tools & methods
 - *Engagement strategies*
 - *level of transparency concerning possible engagement in the innovation process (Galway/De Vita/SCANBALT/Co-act)*
 - *building trust (Van Geenhuizen/iScape)*
 - *proof of a structured way/strategy for active user involvement (iScape/SISCODE/Vitalise/Forum LLSA/Water Europe/SCANBALT/Super MoRRI)*
 - *incentives/rewards for users/stakeholders for their involvement (Forum LLSA/SCIROCCO)*
 - Range tools & methods
 - *Diversity/range of tools & methods for the different phases of the innovation cycle (iScape/SISCODE/SCORE/open Lab/Forum LLSA/Water Europe/SCIROCCO/Super MoRRI)*
 - *Frequency of usage tools & methods (SISCODE)*
 - External communication processes

- *Level of transparent communication about the concept & background, innovation processes and (positive AND negative) results/outcomes (De Vita/iScape/LL Markers/Forum LLSA/SCANBALT/Super MoRRI/Co-act)*
- *Proof of a tailored communication strategy towards the different types of stakeholders (iScape/LL Markers/Forum LLSA/ Water Europe/Super MoRRI/ Co-act)*
- *Range of (technical) communication channels (SCORE/Water Europe)*
- *% success rate of the communication activities (Open Lab)*
- Quality/innovativeness
 - *Quality of tools & methods (SCORE/Open Lab/Co-act)*
 - *Classification of tools & methods (Water Europe)*
 - *Relevance of used tools & methods validated by relevant stakeholders (Super MoRRI/Water Europe)*
- **Impact & value**
 - Co-created values
 - *User satisfaction*
 - *Value of their engagement as users (Habibipour/Hang/Beaudoin/SCORE/Vitalise/ Co-act)*
 - *Value for users to use the innovation (Habibipour)*
 - *Stakeholder satisfaction*
 - *Value creation for ALL stakeholders (Ståhlbröst /Osorio/iScape/SCORE)*
 - *Activities/projects evaluated by all stakeholders (Forum LLSA)*
 - *Knowledge sharing*
 - *Continuous learning & development over time (Ståhlbröst/B-Water Smart/Forum LLSA)*
 - *Frequency of knowledge sharing with relevant actors (SISCODE/SCORE/Open Lab/Forum LLSA/Water Europe/SCANBALT/Super MoRRI/Co-act/various)*
 - *Number of openly shared datasets (Open Lab/various)*
 - *Number of internal knowledge sharing meetings (Open Lab/Vitalise)*
 - *Variety of stakeholders in knowledge sharing activities (Vitalise/Forum LLSA)*
 - *Capacity building*
 - *Hours of training provided by the living lab (SCORE/Open Lab/Vitalise/Super MoRRI)*
 - *Number of open educational resources shared (Open Lab/Vitalise/SCIROCCO/Super MoRRI)*
 - *Numbers of persons trained (Open Lab)*
 - *% success rate of the training activities (Open Lab/Co-act)*
 - *Number of students graduating (Vitalise)*
 - *Number of study credits (Vitalise)*
 - *Promotion of dissemination & transfer of knowledge & skills by users/stakeholders (LL Markers)*
 - *Common understanding between science & society (Co-act)*
 - *technology transfer actions (B-water smart)*
 - *Value capturing strategies*
 - *3 categories of value creation: knowledge, social & business (Fasshauer)*
 - *Transformation of generated knowledge into models, methods & tools (Ståhlbröst, LL Markers)*
 - *TRL level of the developed tools of technologies (Open Lab)*
 - *Analysis of innovation & dissemination potential for each project (Vitalise)*
 - *Value chain coverage*
 - *Economic value for the entire value chain (Mulder/ Ståhlbröst)*
 - *Degree of engagement of the living lab within productive value chains of the given broader innovation ecosystems (iScape)*
 - Impacts
 - *General about impacts*
 - *measurements tend to favor qualitative methods (Ballon)*
 - *tangible & intangible outcomes (Haug)*

- Societal impact
 - Solutions responding to local challenges and opportunities (Gualandi & Romme)
 - Non-financial impact of new products & services (Gualandi & Romme)
 - Changes in mindsets/Modified behavior (Haug/Open Lab/B-Water Smart/Co-act)
 - Social effects caused the living lab (Ståhlbröst)
 - Improved wellbeing of participants (within X years) (Vitalise)
 - Community resilience (Co-act)
 - SDGs (Co-act)
- Environmental impact
 - Positive effects in mobility (reduced emissions, shorter travel times...) (Alonso-Raposo-JRC)
 - Environmental effects caused by the living lab (Ståhlbröst)
 - Measures to protect natural resources (Co-act)
 - Awareness (Open Lab/Co-act)
- Economic impact
 - Company growth (Baccarne/Gualandi & Romme/Super MoRRI)
 - Enhanced competitive advantage (Baccarne/Gualandi & Romme)
 - New business (& market) development (e.g., creation/support of spin-offs/start-ups) (Baccarne/Open Lab/B-Water Smart/SCANBALT/Co-act/Water Europe)
 - Reducing & sharing development risks & costs (Leminen/Vitalise/B-Water Smart/Super MoRRI/Co-act)
 - Economic effects caused by the living lab (Ståhlbröst)
 - Number of licenses awarded (Open Lab)
 - Number of patents (Open Lab/Vitalise/B-Water Smart/Water Europe/various)
 - Structured method for calculating the actual benefits of the technologies or its adoption (Vitalise)
- Regulatory impact
 - Enabling transformation processes within public administration (Haug)
 - Policy impacts achieved (Alonso-Raposo-JRC)
 - Influence policies & regulatory frameworks (SISCODE)
 - Number of changed/implemented policies/directives (Open Lab/Vitalise/B-Water Smart/Co-act)
 - Increase of common understanding between political representatives & the (innovation) ecosystems (Co-act/various)
 - Removal of regulatory barriers (various)
- Internal impact
 - Improvement of organizational working procedures (Beaudoin/SISCODE/Open Lab/Forum LLSA/various)
 - % achievement of desired knowledge & skills of the internal team members (SCORE/Forum LLSA)
- Academic validation
 - Number of scientific outputs (e.g., papers) (Alonso-Raposo-JRC/Vitalise/Open Lab/SISCODE/Co-act)
 - Number of publications/articles (Open Lab/Co-act)
 - Number of PHD grants & contracts (B-Water Smart)
 - Transnational authorship (Vitalise/Co-act)
 - Referrals, awards & recognition of papers (Vitalise/Co-act/various)

Stability & harmonization

- Stability
 - Improved collaborations
 - Creation of networks to collaborate (Haug/Beaudoin/Leminen/Schuurman/LL Markers/SCANBALT)
 - % influence by the LL on other innovation ecosystems (Open Lab)

- *Intensified relationships with their organizational internal customers (Santonen/iScape/Open Lab/B-Water smart)*
- *A reliable partner framework (Santonen/SCORE/vitalise/Forum LLSA/B-Water smart)*
- *Number of new partners involved (in the strategic process) (Leminen/Open Lab/Forum LLSA)*
- **SWOT**
 - *(High level) of financial maturity based on a balanced & diversified set of funding & revenue streams (Santonen/Gualandi & Romme/ Mastelic/iScape/ Open Lab/ Forum LLSA/ B-Water smart/SCIROCCO)*
 - *Definition of new needs after fulfilment of the LL goals (Leminen/Forum LLSA/Co-act)*
 - *Potential ROI of solutions developed (SCORE)*
- **Foresight**
 - *Governance & support processes in place (Kviselius/Guzman/Mastelic/Forum LLSA)*
 - *Mature technical infrastructures & facilities (Santonen)*
 - *Increase of offered R&I activities (Santonen)*
 - *Clearly defined revenue streams (Mastelic/Guzman/iScape/Water Europe/B-Water Smart/SCIROCCO)*
 - *Structured method for measuring the values of services rendered by the LL (Guzman/Vitalise/Forum LLSA)*
 - *Multiple living lab value propositions (Santonen/iScape/Water Europe/Forum LLSA/SCANBALT/B-watersmart/SCIROCCO/Move21/various)*
- **Harmonization & scale-up**
- **Replicability**
 - *Degree of flexibility the living lab can handle with regards to its targets markets (Mulder)*
 - *Identification of possible solutions for replication (SISCOCE/SCORE/Open Lab)*
 - *% partners committed to replicate & upscale solutions (SCORE/Vitalise/B-Water Smart)*
- **Scalability (cross-border/cross-sectoral)**
 - *Number of solutions of the living lab that have been scaled-up/re-used after the experiments (Alonso-Raposo-JRC/iScape/Open Lab/SCORE/LL Markers)*
 - *Adaptation/expansion of (data collection) infrastructure (Water Europe/various)*
 - *Improvement & sharing of living lab services (Santonen/Mulder/LL Markers/Forum LLSA)*
 - *Skills & knowledge transfer to a wider network of actors (Leminen/Mulder/Vitalise/LL Markers/Forum LLSA/Co-act)*
 - *Networking between living labs (Schuurman/Vitalise/Water Europe/Forum LLSA/SCANBALT)*
- **Harmonization**
 - *Harmonized vocabulary (on data infrastructures) (Santonen)*
 - *standardization/harmonization of the living lab infrastructure, activities & services (Leminen/Mulder/Water Europe/SCIROCCO)*
 - *harmonized service creation (Mulder/SCIROCCO)*
 - *harmonized methods & tools (Mulder/Open Lab/Water Europe)*
 - *harmonized procedures (Vitalise/B-Water Smart)*
 - *open & public standards (Vitalise/SCIROCCO)*
 - *number of projects ran with common processes (Vitalise/Water Europe)*
- **Benchmarking**
 - *Quality of knowledge sharing compared to other living labs (Open Lab)*
 - *Quality of capacity building compared to other living labs (Open Lab)*
 - *Living lab activities & solutions meet benchmark European, regional & international standards (Vitalise)*

Appendix 4

Living Lab Mapping Canvas

Interactive canvas for LL / city leaders & representatives to help them develop a sustainable living lab to engage the quadruple helix

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